

Bimodal IT Governance

*A case study on how organizations govern their IT
in a bimodal archetype*

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Management Summary

Moving towards digital transformation (leveraging technology to enable value creation, with impact on an organizations business processes, products and services), many organizations use some form of Bimodal IT. Bimodal IT means managing two separate but coherent styles of work – one focused on predictability and the other on exploration. This research project investigates how organizations govern their IT in such a Bimodal IT setting. The main research question follows logically: *“How do organizations govern their IT in a bimodal archetype?”*

A content analysis from scientific and other literature is conducted, identifying different types of Bimodal IT and identifying key elements required for governance of IT, structures, processes and relational mechanisms (SPRM's), that are specific for a Bimodal IT setting. Next, a case study across eight different organizations deploying some form of Bimodal IT is executed by interviewing a minimum of two senior managers from each organization and requesting supporting documentation regarding the organizations IT governance model.

Based on the theoretical framework derived from literature analysis the case study results are analyzed. The result is a description of how real-world organizations govern their IT in a Bimodal setting. The answer to the main research question is surprisingly simple: *“Through the adoption of structures, processes and relational mechanisms that are suitable and tailored for bimodal environments”*. Notable key elements requiring elaboration in the answer are “suitable” and “tailored”. Suitable meaning the SPRM's are relevant for the specific archetype an organization (currently) has. Tailored should be interpreted as keeping aligned to the inherently dynamic state of organizations, meaning the continuous (small) changes required to address the organizations context, industry type, volumes, market, physical environment, culture etc. etc.

The main findings from this research are:

1. Presence of processes is strong; design effectiveness of processes can be verified. Operational effectiveness of processes is suspected to lag.
2. Knowledge on Bimodal IT, SPRM's and application for enterprise governance of IT is not readily available across organizations. Overall knowledge unconsciously to consciously incompetent.
3. Eight Bimodal IT specific practices have been identified, but further definition and elaboration of these practices is recommended.
4. Traditional top-down decision making is not aligned with mode 2 operation of Bimodal IT
5. Too much governance focus on the development and business areas, leaving (IT) operations getting too little attention.

The corresponding recommendations to mitigate these findings are:

1. Conduct regular (annual) independent audit and/or maturity assessments on selected processes
2. Issue awareness campaigns on governance. Educate key staff on governance of IT. Also, proposal to extend current EGIT definition (Grembergen & Haes, 2015) with: *“skillfully identified and chosen taking into account both the level of digitalization the organization has and can absorb, and the level of business- and IT-savviness present in the organization”*
3. Further research and definition of specific Bimodal IT practices e.g. through Delphi research
4. Allocate specific autonomy in mode 2 teams. Develop decision-making process with flexible balance between top-down structuration and team autonomy.
5. Job rotation between development and operational roles. Co-location of development and operations teams. Integration of operations activities in development teams (DevOps)

We hope you enjoy reading this thesis!
/Geert Gorsel & Marc Teering, June 2018.

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Proud, somewhat tired but overall happy and quite satisfied.

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Abbreviations

AMS	Antwerp Management School
API	Application Protocol Interface
APO	Align, Plan and Organize
BAI	Build, Acquire and Implement
CDO	Chief Digital Officer
CEO	Chief Executive Officer
CIO	Chief Information Officer
COO	Chief Operations Officer
DAD	Disciplined Agile Delivery
DBU	Digital Business Unit
DevOps	A neologism of Development and Operations
DSS	Deliver, Service and Support
EGIT	Enterprise Governance of IT
IoT	Internet of Things
IT	Information Technology
Kanban	Scheduling system for Lean projects
LeSS	Large-Scale Scrum
MEA	Monitor, Evaluate and Assess
Nexus	'Nexus is the exoskeleton of Scrum'
PMBOK	Project Management Body Of Knowledge
PMI	Project Management Institute
PPM	(Bimodal) Program- and Portfolio Management
PRINCE2	PRojects IN Controlled Environments
RACI	Responsible, Accountable, Consulted, Informed
ROI	Return On Investment
SAFe	Scaling Agile Framework
SAFe ART	Scaling Agile Framework, Agile Release Train
SAFe PI event	Scaling Agile Framework, Program Increment event
Scrum	Framework for effective team collaboration
Scrumban	A neologism of Scrum and Kanban
SPRM	Structures, Processes & Relational Mechanisms

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1 Introduction and problem statement

1.1 Research motivation

In the current day and age of globalization, digital consumerization, e-business, cloud computing and the advance of the Internet of Things, there is a push on organizations to be more flexible and responsive on trends, new disruptive entrants and create more efficiency both upstream and downstream in the value chain (Kotter, 2012), (Kotter, 2014). As a result of this, many organizations are looking for ways to shorten the time to market of their digital innovations drastically, whilst keeping their IT systems stable and available. Indeed a major challenge, given the fact that making changes to your digital environment is still the largest source of (IT-)outages and service unavailability, as any CIO will be able to tell you (Kasulke & Bensch, 2017).

In finding these ways, many methods and techniques have been developed (and are still being used), like Agile, Scrum, Lean, DevOps and others. Bottom line of all these is that they are deployed on a speedy, responsive front-end, but on the back-end the legacy systems are still managed and working according to existing methods and standards like waterfall, V-model development & testing and traditional project management methods. The trend is that many organizations are dividing their IT in two parts: a flexible responsive front-end and a stable, more traditional back-end. Since Gartner put the term Bimodal IT on the agenda in 2014 (Mesaglio & Mingay, 2014), the buzz on this Bimodal IT, also referred to in terms like ambidextrous, two-speed, multi-speed or multi-modal IT, has increased. Both with supporting and critical references, but the fact that Bimodal IT is part of a hype and that many organizations are working with some form of this model cannot be denied.

The container reference that brings all of the above together in a broader context is called digital transformation. The transformation is referring to the leap that organizations have to make in order to evolve from “traditional IT” to “digital enterprise” (Ross, Beath, & Sebastian, 2017) The latter can constitute any stage along the path to full digitalization that can be referred to as bimodal, multimodal or another variety. It is typically marked by the fact that traditional IT is not the driver or even completely bypassed by end users (Bygstad, 2015). It is interesting to investigate in which ways organizations foster bimodal archetypes to contribute in the realization of business benefits (value) from the investments in their digital assets.

1.2 Problem definition and research question

Digital Transformation (Gils & Proper, 2017) is ‘hot’ and many companies are struggling to find a way to cope with being innovative, flexible and responsive to market demands while running their core operation/business without unplanned downtime at the same time. These inherently conflicting demands of exploration and exploitation are proving challenging for CIO’s, CDO’s and IT organizations in general. The current trend -or hype- mentioned above, Bimodal IT, claims to deliver a solution to this challenge. Given the fact that IT is recognized to carry the potential to create a key strategic difference in an organization's competitiveness (Venkatraman, Henderson, & Oldach, 1993) the question arises on how organizations use and manage a bimodal archetype to operate their (bimodal) IT organization effectively. How can a Bimodal IT organization be governed and sustained and truly support business goals and render these as key strategic differences in the current turmoil of their competitors (Sheedy & Guarini, 2017). At the same time respond to economic and political changes (Dornberger, 2018) whilst meeting all other legal and moral requirements and resisting the pressure of start-ups and early adopters, that are completely digital due to their greenfield starting point.

Based on the background and challenges as described above, the central research question is:

Central Research Question:
How do organizations govern their IT in a bimodal archetype?

To be able to answer this question, several elements from this question must be explained more in-depth, hence the following supporting questions are formulated:

1. *Governance – what is governance of IT?*
By executing literature research meaning is given to the concept “governance of IT”.
2. *Bimodal archetypes – which archetypes exist and how can they be distinguished?*
From literature research characteristics are identified for the different archetypes of Bimodal IT that exist. Also, meaning is given to the concept of bimodal.
3. *SPRM’s - which specific structures, processes and relational mechanisms can be identified in literature, pertaining to the defined bimodal archetypes?*
Structures, Processes and Relational Mechanisms (SPRM’s) play a key role in governance. Can any SPRM’s be found that are specific for bimodal archetypes? Also, the minimally required SPRM’s to be able to execute governance of IT are identified.
4. *Contribution - in which way do the different archetypes contribute to the realization of governance of Bimodal IT?*
By executing interviews with key stakeholders in different organizations and reviewing the documentation these organizations have, an assessment is done on the effectiveness of governance implementation for different archetypes.

The resulting conceptual framework is shown in figure 1: Conceptual framework. This framework pictures the influence of archetypes (independent variable) on governance of Bimodal IT (dependent variable). This influence is affected by the SPRM’s (moderating variable).

figure 1: Conceptual framework

1.3 Relevance

The scientific relevance of this research is apparent from the fact that next to the abundance of whitepapers and consulting documents, very little scientific research on Bimodal IT is available (Horlach, Drews, Schirmer, & Boehmann, 2017). In this research we follow the recommendation that is suggested in the leading paper “Increasing the Agility of IT Delivery: Five Types of Bimodal IT Organization” (Horlach et al., 2017), suggesting more inputs from different industries and regions.

Social relevance is present for participating and interested organizations. Practices and background are given that can aid in starting or improving deployment of a Bimodal IT archetype in order to increase flexibility and responsiveness. This input can also be used to aid organizations in their process of digital transformation or to create awareness on digital transformation. This to improve organizations overall efficiency and shorten the time to market of products or services that are enabled by IT, thus increasing the value of organizations.

1.4 Reading Guide

To answer the central research question insight is required into governance of IT, bimodal archetypes and the role of SPRM's in governance of IT. In chapter 2 “Methodology and research design” the research methods, techniques and strategy are explained. The relevant underlying theory and scientific backbone to substantiate these elements is described in chapter 3 “Theoretical framework”.

In chapter 4 “Research execution and analysis”, the actual research activities and results are documented. This includes an overview of the research results of all participating organizations. Next, empirical results are confronted against the theoretical framework. In chapter 5 “Conclusions and recommendations” the central research question and supporting questions are answered. Next a synthesis of the results of this research project is provided and suggestions for practical application and further research are given.

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2 Methodology and research design

In this chapter, the research methods and techniques to answer the central research question and the supporting questions are explained. The choice for this methodology is also motivated. Likewise, the way in which the research is constructed is illustrated.

2.1 Research objective

This research can be typed as applied research. It has both an explorative and evaluating objective and thus falls in the category of deductive research because it tests and evaluates existing theory. The explorative element is characterized by the fact that very little scientific research in the area of governance of Bimodal IT organizations exists to date. This is shown by the limited volume of scientific articles that can be found on this subject. This limited volume is confirmed by the statement that “Bimodal IT has rarely been a subject of scientific research” (Horlach et al., 2017).

This research is also evaluating, because it investigates the actual use of Bimodal IT in real organizations. In this way it evaluates the theoretical base that describes how this governance could be structured according to literature. The general objective is to formulate recommendations for the application of Bimodal IT in organizations. Also, the identification of common practices when applying bimodal archetypes is an objective of this research (Thiel, 2015)

2.2 Strategy: case study

The strategy constitutes the framework, the logical structure of scientific research. Within this strategy there are multiple opportunities to gather data. This research has as strategy the case study. To mitigate the challenges involving case study research the principle of triangulation (also referred to as mixed methods) is used (Thiel, 2015). Triangulation means the use of multiple methods of research. In this research content analysis, interviews and multiple researchers are combined.

This research verifies how organizations that deploy a Bimodal IT govern the resulting two speeds at which their IT organization has to run. It also determines to which basic archetype of Bimodal IT this way of governing can be attributed. Finally, this research identifies the common practices amongst the SPRM’s that organizations deploy to execute their governance of Bimodal IT.

2.3 Methods: content analysis and interviews

A choice has been made to collect information through content analysis and conducting interviews with a minimum of two major stakeholders per organization. This is done for a total of eight organizations in different industries and across geographical regions.

Content analysis

For the content analysis existing documentation, presentations and reports from the participating organizations are used. This is so-called primary material (Thiel, 2015). The list of requested materials per organization can be found in Appendix C – List of requested documents.

Interviews

For each organization interviews are conducted with a minimum of two key stakeholders, all of whom are part of senior management in the organization. By interviewing these key stakeholders, a representative image of the way governance is implemented and executed can be described. Shortly before the interviews are held, a brief introduction to Bimodal IT and its archetypes is presented to the interviewee. This introduction can be found in Appendix D – Introduction for interviews.

All interviews are semi-structured interviews, with an introduction to the interview, similar question list and pointers for the interviewer to ask further questions on a topic.

The choice for semi-structured interviews is motivated by the limited time for executing the operational research and the specificity of the topic whilst keeping more flexibility as opposed to questionnaires or fully structured interviews.

2.4 Operationalization

Before starting the interviews, a number of preparing actions has been executed. Literature research on governance (of IT), Bimodal IT and subjects related to or referred to these has been conducted. Based on this research, the theoretical framework was created. In the theoretical framework, the concepts relevant to the central research questions and supporting questions are captured and defined.

More specific, the key elements for governance, structures, processes and relational mechanisms are explained. Context is given to what governance is, and to which role it can or should play in the management of organizations. The relationship between governance and SPRM's is explained. The minimal required set of SPRM's to be able to execute governance (of IT) in an organization is distinguished. Also, the concept of Bimodal IT is analyzed and a division into five basic archetypes is identified. The SPRM's that are specific to Bimodal IT are identified across the five different archetypes. This enables answering supporting questions 1 and 2. This operationalization is shown in the table in Appendix E – Operationalization.

Next, based on this theoretical framework, the interview questions are prepared. These questions cover the complete context of the five different archetypes that have been defined for Bimodal IT. They also cover the complete scope of identified SPRM's relating to all five archetypes. With the interview results supporting question 3 can be answered. The interview questions are also shown in Appendix F – Interview questions.

Finally, interviews are carried out with key stakeholders in different organizations and supporting documentation is requested. By analyzing the interview results and documentation supporting question 4 can be answered.

With all supporting questions answered, it is now possible to answer the central research question and formulate conclusion(s) and recommendations.

2.5 Reliability and validity

Reliability is related to the avoidance of accidental errors and the repeatability of the research. This can be divided into the accuracy and consistency with which variables are measured. Accuracy refers to the measurement instruments, like questionnaires, that are used. Consistency refers to the repeatability of the research; under the same circumstances the same measurement should result in the same finding.

Validity can also be divided in two elements; internal and external validity. Internal validity refers to the research itself. Do we measure the effect that we want to measure? External validity refers to the generalizability of the research; to what extent are the conclusions useable in similar situations.

Specifically, in case study research several sources of interference exist regarding reliability and validity (Thiel, 2015). The most important ones are:

- The limited number of research objects.
- The researcher him- or herself.
- The research method(s). In this case particularly the use of humans as data source.

Several measures can be taken to increase the reliability and validity. In this research the following measures are taken:

- Multiple cases (organizations) are part of this research, with multiple key stakeholders per organization.
- Triangulation is used;
 - content analysis;
 - interviews, where interview questionnaires are the same across organizations and researchers;
 - multiple researchers are combined.
- Interviewees are informed beforehand that the interview will be anonymous and the research is commissioned by education and not by their own management.
- A consistent system to capture interview results across organizations is used.
- Interviews are recorded in order to allow repetition of original data capture.
- The team of two researchers allow for peer feedback.

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3 Theoretical framework

In this chapter the core concepts as mentioned in the central research question and supporting questions are explained, defined and placed into context. Specifically, the concept of governance (of IT) and the distinction between governance and management is covered. Also, the related practices for governance: structures, processes and relational mechanisms are considered. Furthermore, the concept of bimodal is elaborated and divided into five basic archetypes. Finally, SPRM's that are specific for bimodal archetypes are identified from literature. In the concluding paragraph all this theory is merged into a research model.

3.1 Governance, Management and SPRM's

Governance is a word that is used in broad contexts, covering a variety of understandings. According to the Oxford English dictionary, governance means “conduct the policy, actions, and affairs (of something) with authority”. From this definition it is clear that the assets and resources pertaining to information technology in organizations also require governance. Yet, what governance of IT means exactly and by whom or how this should be done is not obvious. These same unclarities apply to management, that is required to be able to exercise governance.

Governance versus management

To be able to differentiate between governance and management, the systems theory of De Leeuw can provide clarification (De Leeuw, 1982). De Leeuw recognizes three roles, the controlling system, the controlled system, and the environment. In this paradigm the board of directors (in Dutch: raad van commissarissen) can be considered as the controlling system and the executive management (in Dutch: raad van bestuur) as the controlled system. This is in line with the definition of governance and management as given in COBIT5: “Governance ensures that stakeholder needs, conditions and options are evaluated to determine balanced, agreed-on enterprise objectives to be achieved; setting direction through prioritization and decision making; and monitoring performance and compliance against agreed-on direction and objectives.” (ISACA.org, 2012). In the ISO38500 standard, governance is described as “The system by which organizations are directed and controlled” (ISO, 2015). The ISO38500 definition is adapted from Cadbury 1992 and OECD 1999, hence shorter, but essentially the tenor of both is the same.

Management is described in COBIT5 as “Management plans, builds, runs and monitors activities in alignment with the direction set by the governance body to achieve the enterprise objectives” (ISACA.org, 2012). In the ISO38500 standard as “The system of controls and processes required to achieve the strategic objectives set by the organization's governing body. Management is subject to the policy guidance and monitoring set through corporate governance” (ISO, 2015). Again, the tenor of both is the same.

COBIT considers governance as primary task of the board of directors, led by a chairperson and management as primary task of executive management, led by the CEO. Of course, also executive management can be considered the controlling system and the organization of which it is the governing body as the controlled system. Context and perspective are relevant when discussing governance. It is clear that in exercising governance both elements (governance and management) are relevant. It is also clear that exercising governance requires management. This decomposition can be applied to governance and management all the way down to individual structures, processes and relational mechanisms, each of which will have a governance and management component.

figure 2: Systems theory of De Leeuw

Governance of IT

Notwithstanding the serious budgets and increasing importance of information technology to the performance of organizations (Venkatraman et al., 1993) surprisingly little attention is given to governing IT assets and resources on a corporate level. For example, in the revised G20/OECD Principles of Corporate Governance, issued 2015, no mention of governing IT is made in chapter six, discussing “The responsibilities of the board” (G20 / OECD, 2015). This comes as a surprise, given the fact that according to literature governance of IT will enable alignment (between business and IT) and only this alignment will enable value creation from investments in IT (Grembergen & Haes, 2015). The link between organizational performance and IT performance is recognized (Venkatraman et al., 1993). Hence, clarification of the meaning of governance of IT is required.

Quite some research has been performed into governance of IT. An important conclusion that is broadly shared by researchers is that there is no silver bullet. A common best governance method or model for IT governance does not exist (Brown, Grant, & Sprott, 2005). Different streams and archetypes have been identified, resulting in areas of importance with regard to decision making for IT, like IT investment and prioritization, IT principles and IT infrastructure strategies. Also, how organizations come to making decisions and by whom is decomposed into archetypes. Think of Feudal, IT duopoly, IT monarchy and the likes (Weill, 2004). Even critical success factors have been identified (Weill, 2004), (Grembergen & Haes, 2015) and an ISO standard for IT Governance (38500) has been established.

Specific definitions for governing IT have been given by Weil; “IT governance represents the framework for decision rights and accountabilities to encourage desirable behavior in the use of IT” (Weill, 2004), (Weill & Ross, 2004). Also, by the IT Governance Institute (ITGI); “IT Governance is the responsibility of the Board of Directors and executive management. IT is an integral part of enterprise governance and consists of the leadership and organizational structures and processes that ensure that the organization’s IT sustains and extends the organization’s strategy and objectives” and in the ISO38500 standard: “The system by which the current and future use of IT is directed and controlled. Corporate governance of IT involves evaluating and directing the use of IT to support the organization and monitoring this use to achieve plans. It includes the strategy and policies for using IT within an organization.”

Since value can only be created on the business side of an organization, involvement of business is essential in the governance of IT. As a result, involvement of board level executives in governing an organization’s IT becomes imperative. Therefore, this research uses as definition the concept of Enterprise Governance of IT (EGIT), as defined by Van Grembergen and De Haes: “Enterprise Governance of IT is an integral part of corporate governance, exercised by the Board, overseeing the definition and implementation of processes, structures and relational mechanism in the organization that enable both business and IT people to execute their responsibilities in support of business/IT alignment and the creation of business value from IT-enabled business investments” (Grembergen & Haes, 2015).

Implementing EGIT - Structures, Processes and Relational Mechanisms

Next challenge lies in how to deploy Enterprise Governance of IT (EGIT). Enter the concept of Structures, Processes and Relational Mechanisms (SPRM’s). To create a practically applicable governance deployment model, organizations must deploy a mixture of these SPRM’s that is tailored to the organizations context as a whole (Grembergen & Haes, 2015).

Examples of Structures are IT committees, reporting lines of IT executives and organizational units. Processes are centered around IT decision making and monitoring, e.g. portfolio management and cost control. Finally, relational Mechanisms involve partnering, collaboration and participation. Examples are co-locating business and IT people or purposely mixing different organizational units by allocating them to a shared company restaurant.

Once again, there is no silver bullet; even though essential SPRM's for Bimodal IT have been identified in this research project, tailor-made solutions (SPRM combinations) for each organization are required. These solutions must be kept up to date over time and thus are inherently somewhat dynamic. They should always address the organizations context, industry type, volumes, market, physical environment, culture etc. etc. The essential SPRM's that constitute the minimal required set to be able to exercise EGIT are listed in the table below. The complete list of SPRM's can be found in Appendix G – 33 EGIT practices (Grembergen & Haes, 2015).

Index	IT governance practice	Definition
S1	IT strategy committee at level of board of directors	<i>Committee at level of board of directors to ensure IT is regular agenda item and reporting issue for the board of directors</i>
S4	CIO on executive committee	<i>CIO is a full member of the executive committee</i>
S5	CIO (Chief Information Officer) reporting to CEO (Chief Executive Officer) and/or COO (Chief Operational Officer)	<i>CIO has a direct reporting line to the CEO and/or COO</i>
S6	IT steering committee (IT investment evaluation / prioritization at executive / senior management level)	<i>Steering committee at executive or senior management level responsible for determining business priorities in IT investments.</i>
S9	IT project steering committee	<i>Steering committee composed of business and IT people focusing on prioritizing and managing IT projects</i>
P1	Strategic information systems planning	<i>Formal process to define and update the IT strategy</i>
P3	Portfolio management (incl. business cases, information economics, ROI, payback)	<i>Prioritization process for IT investments and projects in which business and IT is involved (incl. business cases)</i>
P8	Project governance / management methodologies	<i>Processes and methodologies to govern and manage IT projects</i>
P9	IT budget control and reporting	<i>Processes to control and report upon budgets of IT investments and projects</i>
R8	IT leadership	<i>Ability of CIO or similar role to articulate a vision for IT's role in the company and ensure that this vision is clearly understood by managers throughout the organization</i>

table 1: Minimum required SPRM's from (Grembergen & Haes, 2015)

This concept of SPRM's is not only found in the research of Van Grembergen and De Haes (Grembergen & Haes, 2015), but is also present in the ISO38500 standard, according to its six principles, that can be mapped to SPRM's:

- Principle 1 – Responsibility. Referring to roles and responsibilities, having an appropriate RACI. This can be considered as structures
- Principles 2-5 – Strategy, Acquisition, Performance and Conformance. These practices can be considered processes, that in turn can be divided into sub-processes from various supporting domains like ITIL v3 or COBIT5 APO, BAI, DSS or MEA.
- Principle 6 – Human Behavior. Referring to the need to identify and appropriately consider the different human behaviors and associated needs. The related practices can be considered relational mechanisms.

In the ISACA COBIT5 model similar aspects are mentioned in enterprise enablers:

- Processes describe an organized set of practices and activities to achieve certain objectives and produce a set of outputs in support of achieving overall IT-related goals.
- Organizational structures are the key decision-making entities in an enterprise.
- Culture, ethics and behavior of individuals and of the enterprise are very often underestimated as a success factor in governance and management activities (ISACA.org, 2012).

3.2 Introduction to Bimodal

Bimodal IT is a concept that is used by many companies worldwide in their journey towards digital transformation. Digital transformation, also known as digitalization (Ross et al., 2017), refers to the effects that integration and adaptation of information technology can have on an organizations business model, products, processes and organizational structure (Hess, Benlian, Matt, & Wiesböck, 2016). The term Bimodal IT that was introduced by Gartner in 2014 refers to having two modes of IT. Mode 1 is traditional, emphasizing safety and accuracy. Mode 2 is non-sequential, emphasizing agility and speed (Mesaglio & Mingay, 2014).

Next to Bimodal IT, a number of other terms are used in literature, that more or less refer to the same concept.

Term	Explanation
Bimodal IT (Gartner)	The practice of managing two separate but coherent styles of work – one focused on predictability and the other on exploration. Mode 1 is traditional, emphasizing safety and accuracy. Mode 2 is non-sequential, emphasizing agility and speed. (Mingay & Mesaglio, 2016).
Multi-speed IT (Accenture)	A blend of various delivery approaches that bring together different layers of technology—from fast-changing digital applications to decades-old legacy systems—developing at different speeds, to deliver business outcomes. It requires the technology function to use a mix of processes, tools (DevOps, Agile) and technologies, while also allowing greater alignment with business strategy (Ram, 2017).
Ambidextrous / Ambidexterity	Refers to the inherently conflicting responsibilities of an IT organization to engage in both exploitative (mode 1) and explorative (mode 2) activities. This results in combined need for IT managers to employ ambidextrous resolution strategies to ensure short-term IT contributions and continuous progress of IT projects while simultaneously working toward IT transformation program success as a foundation for IT-enabled business transformation (Gregory, Keil, Muntermann, & Mähring, 2015).

Term	Explanation
Multimodal IT (Anderson MacGyver)	Essentially a refinement of Bimodal IT. They base the approach to take on the division of governance according to the business domain, the subculture and the type of (IT) service required. This results in 4 types business domains, subcultures and IT service types. The orientation on the extremes (Common / mode 1 and Innovation / mode 2) resembles Bimodal IT. The added elements in the 2-by-2 grid (Craft / Value-Add) are refinements of both modes, made specific for certain context and organizational situation. The mapping of this “multimodal-grid” on organizations is done by using the theory of the operating modal Canvas (Sprokholt, Haijenga, & Boersen, 2015).
Two-speed IT (McKinsey)	This implies a fast-speed, customer-centric front end running alongside a slow-speed, transaction-focused legacy back end. For software-release cycles and deployment mechanisms, the customer-facing part should be modular, to enable quick deployment of new software by avoiding time-consuming integration work. In contrast, the transactional core systems of record must be designed for stability and high-quality data management, which leads to longer release cycles (Blumberg, Bossert, & Laartz, 2016), (Swaminathan & Meffert, 2017).

table 2: Terms used in literature, that are more or less the same as Bimodal IT

For practical reasons and given the fact that the terms used in the table above amount for a great part to similar aspects the term Bimodal IT and the Gartner definition are used in this research. Henceforth Bimodal IT is considered the practice of managing two separate but coherent styles of work – one focused on predictability and the other on exploration. The next step is to distinguish between different types of Bimodal IT.

3.3 Five different archetypes of Bimodal IT

Which archetypes exist is discussed in three papers. The fact that Bimodal IT is a key tool as a transformation step to enable digital transformation is recognized (Haffke, Kalgovas, & Benlian, 2017a). Some papers recognize four archetypes (Haffke et al., 2017a), some three archetypes (Haffke, Kalgovas, & Benlian, 2017b) and even five archetypes (Horlach et al., 2017). Upon closer examination of these papers it becomes clear they all essentially describe the same four archetypes. The fifth archetype that is defined (Horlach et al., 2017) covers what can be considered a nascent state of Bimodal IT where only some development projects within the traditional IT organization are beginning to use agile techniques. Next each archetype is described, based on these three papers.

Archetype 1: Traditional IT with Bimodal development processes

Bimodality is limited to the traditional development process, that uses both traditional (waterfall) and agile methods. This is done for all development, both covering systems of record and customer centric information systems (Horlach et al., 2017). All architecture, testing and operation processes but also other business management processes, continue to use the waterfall methodology. There are no processes that characterize this archetype. There are two relational mechanisms that characterize this archetype: knowledge sharing is done by the developers during handover and business IT alignment mainly takes place between the project manager and the project team. The structures used in this archetype are the same structures that are used in traditional IT governance; boards (or steering committees) for traditional project- and portfolio management (Grembergen & Haes, 2015) and boards for making decisions on overall standards and architectural aspects.

figure 3: Archetype 1, Traditional IT with Bimodal development processes

Archetype 2: Traditional IT with Agile IT Outsourcing

Within archetype 2 there is a partly outsourced IT organization. (Horlach et al., 2017). Development of some projects is outsourced external or through a subsidiary. Sometimes external staff is seated inhouse for alignment purposes. To manage these external providers and assure alignment, outsourcing contracts and agreements are made. Outsourcing is used to become more agile and demonstrate IT capable of shortening time to market. Within the organization an internal project steering committee is established. This internal project steering committee also supplies the alignment with the business through requirements engineering. Budgets are controlled per Business project for the Agile projects. Portfolio management is quite complex since the several business units have their own business portfolio and IT is responsible for condensing these separate portfolios into one IT portfolio.

figure 4: Archetype 2, Traditional IT with Agile IT Outsourcing

Archetype 3: Bimodal Sourcing IT

Archetype 3 is defined as where the organization is outsourcing one or even two bimodal modes (Horlach et al., 2017). Outsourcing can be done in two ways. The first way by using a client – supplier variant where corporate IT acts as governance instance during the development phase. Steering

figure 5: Archetype 3, Bimodal Sourcing with or without project management

committee is on corporate level, planning and governance processes are executed in a waterfall way. Steering takes place, based upon contracts and agreements. Most essential are the requirements that the client (IT) delivers to the supplier. The second way is through an internal project organization. This way is characterized by a complete internal governance structure, with steering committees, and a separate project portfolio management. The project managers are internally supplied and decide per project on the used methodology (Agile or traditional). In this project organization, budgets are also controlled per project. The project managers must be able to run projects in both modes. Business-IT alignment lies merely with the individual project managers and formally with the steering committee. External suppliers deliver skilled resources. A project management office or a project coordinator provides the alignment across the projects that run within the entire organization, often together with a

dedicated business program manager. Both types (client-supplier and internal project organization) can cover development activities as well as activities that are part of ongoing daily operations.

Archetype 4: Bimodal IT

In archetype 4 an organizational type is defined where the delivery modes are separated including their structures and processes (Horlach et al., 2017). Mode 1, traditional IT, led by the CIO, mainly functionally structured. Mode 2, Agile IT, led by the CDO, is a separate organization with small teams, focusing on fast delivery of business outcomes. Scrum, the use of a product owner, scrum master and methods like DevOps are common. Bimodal skill development for staff is facilitated via regular trainings, usually organized through HR. Frameworks like SAFe (Leffingwell, 2017) are also commonly used. Architectural concepts like micro-services and the use of API's are widespread. Corporate management still uses traditional Management structures for their governance, standard steering committees are the interaction with the business. Insourcing is done, mainly on specific technical expertise. Business/IT Alignment is achieved by using a product owner from the business within the projects, and also due to the cooperation between the CIO and the CDO. The role of a CDO is researched (Haffke, Kalgovas, & Benlian, 2016). No unanimous answer to whether a CDO is necessary is given. The coverage of archetype 4 extends beyond development and normal daily operations directly into business units.

figure 6: Archetype 4, Bimodal IT with or without Digital Business Units

Archetype 5: Agile IT

This archetype characterizes itself by an internal unimodal agile IT organization, with small autonomous interdisciplinary teams, responsible for requirements, development, operations but also quality and assurance (Horlach et al., 2017). No communicational overhead or long running projects.

figure 7: Archetype 5, Agile IT with or without Digital Business Units

These Agile teams are responsible for the team composition, decision structures and the overall team mission. Alignment with the business is provided by the (business) product owner who is part of the team. Organizing teams into Digital Business Units increases business IT alignment. The business is involved in product portfolio management processes and also in meetings for budgeting new products. The decisions on budgets are product-driven and not project-driven. Each Digital Business Unit sets its own targets, and each team sets its own goals and is responsible for achieving these goals. Business Unit managers exist solely in a coaching capacity for the teams. Steering and the determination at company level is more or less traditional, but Business and IT are organized

together within the Digital Business Units, so corporation is natural. This is enforced by a shared code of conduct. Decisions are product oriented, not project oriented. Scaled Agile models, like Spotify (Kniberg Henrik; Ivarsson Anders, 2012), with use of Squads, Tribes, Chapters and Guilds, are widely used. Knowledge sharing is done in so called Guilds. A dedicated supervisor is responsible for personnel development. The coverage of this archetype extends beyond development and normal daily operations directly into business units.

3.4 SPRM's that are specific for Bimodal IT

As mentioned in paragraph 3.1, to create an effective governance deployment model, organizations must deploy a mixture of SPRM's. This applies also to governance in organizations with Bimodal IT. Next to the generic IT governance practices as described by Van Grembergen and De Haes (Grembergen & Haes, 2015), specific SPRM's for Bimodal IT can be identified. The fact that generic practices can also be applied in organizations with a bimodal archetype is undisputed.

Aggregation of SPRM's into Bimodal governance practices & mapping on archetypes

For all five archetypes, as described in the various scientific papers (Horlach et al., 2017), (Haffke et al., 2017a), (Haffke et al., 2017b), the case studies have been analyzed and SPRM's have been identified. As mentioned earlier, the available scientific research is scarce. Fortunately, also consulting firms have done research on Bimodal IT. Next to the SPRM's identified in the scientific papers describing the five basic archetypes, a considerable list of whitepapers, publications and consulting research from leading consulting firms with specific expertise in this area is available. The list of papers includes companies like Anderson MacGyver, Forrester, Gartner, McKinsey and Accenture. These whitepapers, publications and consulting research have also been analyzed for SPRM's and these have been added to the list. The complete list of identified SPRM's, 175 in total, and their originating papers can be found in Appendix H – Complete list of all SPRM's found in literature.

All SPRM's identified in this research have been categorized according to the archetype to which they belong and whether they primarily constitute a governance or management activity. Next, all these SPRM's have been related to the 33 original SPRM's as defined by Van Grembergen and De Haes (Grembergen & Haes, 2015) and attributed to the domain where they emerge: in development, in operations or in (collaboration with) business, or a combination of these domains. As a final step, based on the categorization that was made, SPRM's have been grouped into similar SPRM's. Based on this grouping a total of thirty-six practices were identified, eight of which are specific Bimodal IT governance practices. A description of these specific practices is given next. For the identified practices 2, 5, 7 and 8 references have been found in recent scientific research. Practices 1, 3,4 and 6 have been identified solely based on this research project.

Structures
<p>1. <i>Specific Agile roles in job structures and formal documentation of corresponding responsibilities.</i> Across several documents and case studies references are made to the creation and formal inclusion in the organizational function house of specific roles and responsibilities originating from mode 2 oriented methods or techniques. Sometimes grown organically, sometimes implemented with specific purpose.</p>
<p>2. <i>Digital expertise and clear division of accountabilities at executive level between exploitation and exploration collaborating towards business and IT convergence.</i> Where the CIO-role has been evolving from a technical manager via business manager with technical focus to a business visionary, the emergence of the CDO is showing as primarily a business role. The practice beholds both a tight alignment between business roles with a technology leverage focus (whether they are named CDO or not) and a mode 2 IT leadership role (as CIO or with another title) with an agility focus (Haffke et al., 2017b). Each role type requires both substantial business-savviness and IT-savviness.</p>

table 3: Bimodal governance practices – Structures

Processes	
3.	Adapted funding principles tailored to rapid Agile delivery cycles. Budgets and required funding for mode 2 activities have a different flow and dynamic that does not run with the same heartbeat as traditional budgeting cycles. In several cases, the required funding and budgets are allocated outside or next to the traditional cycles.
4.	Agile practices used as replacement of traditional project management techniques and methods. Where traditional methods for project management such as Prince2 or PMBoK (PMI) are tailored for mode 1 activities and have a substantial (administrative) overhead and (time-consuming) tollgate structure, the shorter, iterative cycles and feedback loops of agile-type methods and techniques are introduced to speed up processes and reduce time-to-market.
5.	Business integration practices to enable converging business and IT in structure and strategy To overcome having an agile mode 1 running, but decisions still follow a (mode-2-like) top-down path requiring (senior) management attention instead of being made in the agile empowered teams, rebalancing governance processes, mainly for portfolio- and project management, is required (Horlach & Drews, 2018).
6.	Nontraditional metrics focused on digital adoption and external value creation. Traditional KPI's and other measurements do not match the approach in mode 2. New metrics, e.g. (contribution to) value to the customer are required.

table 4: Bimodal governance practices – Processes

Relational Mechanisms	
7.	Development of IT- and Business-Convergence in the organization (Horlach & Drews, 2018). To facilitate moving beyond Business-IT alignment and embed the governance decision structures in an organization moving towards full digital transformation, a balance must be found between autonomy and authorization for mode 2 activities (Horlach & Drews, 2018).
8.	IT originating body taking the lead in bidirectional collaboration between Business and IT to enable convergence (Horlach & Drews, 2018). This practice refers to initiatives that originate from the (traditional) IT organization, taking business counterparts by the hand in alignment activities, regardless of the fact on which side (business or IT) the accountability should be allocated. A similar practice, originating from the CIO-office, was described in the study case for KLM by Van Grembergen and De Haes (Grembergen & Haes, 2015).

table 5: Bimodal governance practices – Relational Mechanisms

Concluding it is also relevant to mention that from the 33 original SPRM's as identified by Van Grembergen and De Haes (Grembergen & Haes, 2015), a total of six has not been identified in the literature analysis conducted for this research. These SPRM's are listed in the table below.

Index	IT governance practice	Definition
S3	(IT) audit committee at level of board of directors	Independent committee at level of board of directors overseeing (IT) assurance activities
S10	IT security steering committee	Steering committee composed of business and IT people focusing on IT related risks and security issues
P6	IT governance framework COBIT	Process based IT governance and control framework
P7	IT governance assurance and self-assessment	Regular self-assessments or independent assurance activities on the governance and control over IT
P10	Benefits management and reporting	Processes to monitor the planned business benefits during and after implementation of the IT investments / projects.
R4	Knowledge management (on IT governance)	Systems (intranet, ...) to share and distribute knowledge about IT governance framework, responsibilities, tasks, etc.

table 6: SPRM's not identified in literature analysis

3.5 Combining archetypes and practices into a research model

To create a research model, the relationships between the 33 traditional governance practices, the total of 36 identified practices in Bimodal IT settings and the 8 Bimodal IT specific governance practices are visualized in figure 8 below. (A more detailed view of this figure is available in Appendix L – SPRM mapping) For the analysis of the case study results the perceived effectiveness and the perceived ease of implementation of practices is also taken into account. This is done based on the ranking of their perceived effectiveness and perceived ease of implementation as listed in table 7: 33 EGIT practices and their perceived effectiveness and ease of implementation (De Haes & Van Grembergen, 2008).

figure 8: SPRM mapping

Index	IT governance practice	Definition	Perceived effectiveness	Perceived ease of implementation
S1	IT strategy committee at level of board of directors	Committee at level of board of directors to ensure IT is regular agenda item and reporting issue for the board of directors	14	10
S2	IT expertise at level of board of directors	Members of the board of directors have expertise and experience regarding the value and risk of IT	23	32
S3	(IT) audit committee at level of board of directors	Independent committee at level of board of directors overseeing (IT) assurance activities	22	9
S4	CIO on executive committee	CIO is a full member of the executive committee	3	8
S5	CIO (Chief Information Officer) reporting to CEO (Chief Executive Officer) and/or COO (Chief Operational Officer)	CIO has a direct reporting line to the CEO and/or COO	2	1
S6	IT steering committee (IT investment evaluation / prioritisation at executive / senior management level)	Steering committee at executive or senior management level responsible for determining business priorities in IT investments.	1	11
S7	IT governance function / officer	Function in the organisation responsible for promoting, driving and managing IT governance processes	25	16
S8	Security / compliance / risk officer	Function responsible for security, compliance and/or risk, which possibly impacts IT	19	2
S9	IT project steering committee	Steering committee composed of business and IT people focusing on prioritising and managing IT projects	7	3
S10	IT security steering committee	Steering committee composed of business and IT people focusing on IT related risks and security issues	28	7
S11	Architecture steering committee	Committee composed of business and IT people providing architecture guidelines and advise on their applications.	24	15
S12	Integration of governance/alignment tasks in roles & responsibilities	Documented roles & responsibilities include governance/alignment tasks for business and IT people (cf. Weill)	21	26
P1	Strategic information systems planning	Formal process to define and update the IT strategy	11	21
P2	IT performance measurement (e.g. IT balanced scorecard)	IT performance measurement in domains of corporate contribution, user orientation, operational excellence and future orientation	8	23
P3	Portfolio management (incl. business cases, information economics, ROI, payback)	Prioritisation process for IT investments and projects in which business and IT is involved (incl. business cases)	5	25
P4	Charge back arrangements - total cost of ownership (e.g. activity based costing)	Methodology to charge back IT costs to business units, to enable an understanding of the total cost of ownership	18	30
P5	Service level agreements	Formal agreements between business and IT about IT development projects or IT operations	15	14
P6	IT governance framework COBIT	Process based IT governance and control framework	17	28
P7	IT governance assurance and self-assessment	Regular self-assessments or independent assurance activities on the governance and control over IT	31	27
P8	Project governance / management methodologies	Processes and methodologies to govern and manage IT projects	6	18
P9	IT budget control and reporting	Processes to control and report upon budgets of IT investments and projects	4	4
P10	Benefits management and reporting	Processes to monitor the planned business benefits during and after implementation of the IT investments / projects.	26	31
P11	COSO / ERM	Framework for internal control	33	33
R1	Job-rotation	IT staff working in the business units and business people working in IT	32	29
R2	Co-location	Physically locating business and IT people close to each other	30	17
R3	Cross-training	Training business people about IT and/or training IT people about business	29	20
R4	Knowledge management (on IT governance)	Systems (intranet, ...) to share and distribute knowledge about IT governance framework, responsibilities, tasks, etc.	20	24
R5	Business/IT account management	Bridging the gap between business and IT by means of account managers who act as in-between	13	12
R6	Senior business and IT management acting as "partners"	Executive / senior management giving the good example	10	22
R7	Informal meetings between business and IT executive/ senior management	Informal meetings, with no agenda, where business and IT senior management talk about general activities, directions, etc. (e.g. during informal lunches)	12	5
R8	IT leadership	Ability of CIO or similar role to articulate a vision for IT's role in the company and ensure that this vision is clearly understood by managers throughout the organisation	9	19
R9	Corporate internal communication addressing IT on a regular basis	Internal corporate communication regularly addresses general IT issues.	16	6
R10	IT governance awareness campaigns	Campaigns to explain to business and IT people the need for IT governance	27	13

table 7: 33 EGIT practices and their perceived effectiveness and ease of implementation

The resulting combination presented below in figure 9 constitutes the research model. This model, combined with the perceived effectiveness and perceived ease of implementation of practices will be used in the analysis of the data.

figure 9: 36 Bimodal IT governance practices

Explanation of signs:

- BGS1 Essential (Bimodal) SPRM, found both in literature analysis and case organizations
- P8 Essential (Bimodal) SPRM, found both in literature analysis (but not for this archetype!) and case organizations
- BGP4 (Bimodal) SPRM, found both in literature analysis and case organizations
- P5 (Bimodal) SPRM, found both in literature analysis (but not for this archetype!) and case organizations
- S9 Essential (Bimodal) SPRM, found in literature analysis but not present in case organizations
- R10 (Bimodal) SPRM, found in literature analysis but not present in case organizations

4 Research execution and analysis

For the execution of the research, a total of eight organizations have been contacted that recognize (or at least claim) to operate two different speeds in their IT. The table below gives a brief overview of the organizations in size, type and industry. The interviewees have been added, including their reporting distance to the executive committee (Dutch: raad van bestuur).

Overview of case study organizations				
ID	Size	Industry	Reporting distance to Executive Committee	
			Interviewee 1 Focus IT	Interviewee 2 Focus Business
Organization A	1800 emp.	Local Government	+1	+2
Organization B	60 emp.	Finance	0	0
Organization C	6000 emp.	Retail	+1	+2
Organization D	36000 emp.	Government	+2 +3 +3	+2
Organization E	63000 emp.	Government	+2	+2
Organization F	50 emp.	Semi-Government	0 0	0
Organization G	1900 emp.	Semi-Government	+1	+1
Organization H	16250 emp.	Insurance	+2	+1

table 8: Overview Case Study Organizations

All organizations have a sizable IT environment, regardless of their employee volumes. In each organization a minimum of two employees, both working at senior management level have been interviewed. Where possible, a business manager as well as an IT manager has been interviewed. In cases where this proved not possible, an IT manager with a specific business relationship management or account management role was sought. All interviews used the same semi-structured questionnaire, with ample room for asking additional or in-depth questions. All interviews have been recorded to allow exact replication of answers in case of doubt during analysis. The semi-structured question list can be found in Appendix F – Interview questions.

Case study organization typology

1. Case organization A is the IT part of local government of a medium to large city in the Netherlands. They deliver all common municipal services supporting the approximately 1800 employees that serve the city. Also, services directly accessible to end-users (citizens) are in scope. Total turnover is of the organization is € 800 MM.
2. Case organization B is a financial service provider that is part of an extensive industrial conglomerate. They concentrate and optimize worldwide payment flows, manage financial risks, handle financing and refinancing and assure central settlement of payments. The total equity was € 2500 MM in 2017.
3. Case organization C is a retail organization operating as a 1-stop shop across thirty European countries. They have a strong online sales channel and physical presence in most of the countries, either through their own brands or through subsidiaries. They employ some 6000 employees and their turnover is € 560 MM in 2017.

4. Case organization D is a public service, under the political responsibility of a Dutch Ministry with approximately 36.000 employees. About 3.500 are working in IT and a total IT budget for 2018 of approximately € 550 MM.
5. Case organization E is a public service, under the political responsibility of a Dutch Ministry with approximately 63.000 employees. About 2250 are working in IT and a total IT budget for 2018 of approximately € 600 MM.
6. Case organization F is a government datacenter that delivers Housing-, Hosting-, Storage-, PaaS- and SaaS-services to national, local and regional public services. At organization 6 are approximately 50 people working, all within IT with a turnover of € 20 MM in 2017.
7. Case organization G is a non-departmental public body, under the political responsibility of a Dutch Ministry. At organization 7 there are approximately 1900 employees. About 300 people are working within IT. The annual revenue is € 280 MM.
8. Case organization H is an insurance organization that has several subsidiaries/brands. IT is managed centrally and partly within the subsidiaries. The holding has approximately 15.000 employees within the Netherlands and 2.500 employees abroad. The central IT department holds 1250 employees while the subsidiary that was involved in this research, holds approximately 750 employees. The annual turnover in 2015 was € 114 MM.

4.1 Research execution – reporting empirical data

In this paragraph a general overview is given of the interview results and the subsequent further investigation based on received literature and interviews combined.

Overall, we found that out of eight organizations claiming to work with two speeds in their IT, they all engage in having two different paces in their IT. In some organizations the volumes between mode 1 and mode 2 activities differ largely, but they all deploy a form of Bimodal IT. Of the case study organizations, four resemble Bimodal IT archetype 4, two resemble archetype 5, and one resembles archetype 1 respectively archetype 3.

From the identified 36 governance practices in Bimodal IT settings (condensed from 175 identified SPRM's), the two organizations resembling archetypes in the earlier stages of Bimodal IT (archetypes 1-3) have a significantly lower presence of practices (respectively 12 and 18 practices) than the six organizations resembling archetypes 4 and 5 (between 24 and 32).

The division of the identified practices across the SPRM's is also interesting. The 36 identified governance practices for Bimodal IT contain thirteen structures, thirteen processes and ten relational mechanisms. Once again, there is a significant difference between the earlier stages of Bimodal IT and the archetypes 4 and 5; for structures only 2-3 structures for archetypes 1-3 and 8-11 structures for archetypes 4 and 5. Processes have 10 or less for archetypes 1-3 and a 10 or more for archetypes 4 and 5. Lastly for relational mechanisms, the balance is more level with 5 for archetypes 1-3 and 6-9 for archetypes 4 and 5. Details as described in this section are visualized in figure 10: Total amount of governance practices found, per organization.

figure 10: Total amount of governance practices found, per organization

Finally, also the division across the identified governance practices that are specific for Bimodal IT is made. Here, from a total of eight identified specific governance practices (two structures, four processes and three relational mechanisms), archetypes 1-3 deploy no structures where archetypes 4 and 5 deploy 2 structures. Processes are 1 (archetype 1) and 3 (archetype 3) as opposed to 2 to 4 processes for all 4-5 organizations. Relational Mechanisms are more evenly spread, with only 1 organization deploying only 1 mechanism and all others 2. The results are below in figure 11: Total amount of bimodal governance practices found, per organization.

figure 11: Total amount of bimodal governance practices found, per organization

The complete division of all practices is given in the overview table in Appendix K – SPRM distribution across Bimodal governance practices.

4.2 Research analysis – confronting empirical data and theory

In this paragraph, the case study results are confronted against the minimal required practices (SPRM's) needed to exercise governance. This is done including the specific bimodal governance practices, that partly overlap with the minimal required set as defined by Van Grembergen and De Haes (Grembergen & Haes, 2015). Next, a holistic comparison is made from the case study results against the whole palette of 36 bimodal governance practices and a specific analysis view is made for structures, processes and relational mechanisms separately. This analysis is finetuned against the perceived ease of effectiveness and perceived ease of implementation (De Haes & Van Grembergen, 2008). This facilitates understanding of choices that are made by organizations and enables determination of successful practices.

Minimal requirements for governance

According to theory, a minimal required set of practices that must be deployed to be able to exercise governance has been determined (Grembergen & Haes, 2015). When confronting the case study organizations against this minimal set, enhanced with the added essential governance practices identified in this research project (see figure 8: SPRM mapping or Appendix L – SPRM mapping) the results are encouraging with only one organization scoring less than 9 out of 14 essential practices and seven out of eight case study organizations scoring between 9-13. Striking is the relative high presence of processes. This will be elaborated in the section where we discuss the perceived ease of implementation of governance structures. This is visualized in figure 12: Total amount of essential governance practices found, per organization below.

figure 12: Total amount of essential governance practices found, per organization

Complete overview of Bimodal IT governance practices

In the next figure 13: Total amount of governance practices found, per organization the practices as found in the case study organizations are confronted against all SPRM's from literature. The observations are similar to the figure above, with a striking presence of governance processes. Relational mechanisms are scarcely present in the 1-3 archetype organization. Structures are strongly present in archetypes 4 and 5, varying between 8-11 out of 13 structures.

figure 13: Total amount of governance practices found, per organization

Bimodal IT governance practices – structures

Significant when looking at structures is the limited presence of structures in archetypes 1-3. The structures that are present in archetype 1 (S6, S9) are both essential structures that are present in all organizations. Both are perceived as effective (rank 1 respectively rank 7) and easy to implement (rank 11 respectively rank 11). Looking at the remaining structures, notable is that only in one organization (archetype 5, with the greater part of IT running in mode 2) an IT executive committee (S1, deemed essential) is present. None of the organizations have an executive level, fully integrated, committee, board or office for project- respectively portfolio management where business and IT regularly set priorities together, based on business priorities. (relate to S6, S9, S12). One organization specifically mentioned they had tried this, but it turned out to be impossible to integrate, due to lack of knowledge and understanding across domains in this governing body. Their solution was to split into separate domains, hereby solving the integration challenge for the domain, but losing the overall holistic approach. Similar challenges have been noted in other case study organizations. The (lack of) both IT-savviness and business-savviness can be pointed out as the root cause for these issues. This can also be seen in the (absence of) digital savviness at senior executive level, where digital (or IT) savviness, meaning the ability to understand the impact technology can have on business processes, products and services, is scarce. This is further evident in the fact that technology (IT) is not often enough recognized as an enabler for business growth and value creation. Nonetheless, all organizations deploy a form of traditional project management board or steering committee, sometimes managing both mode 1 and mode 2 activities.

Bimodal IT governance practices – processes

The strong presence of processes across all organizations is striking. Although out of scope for this research, a suspicion regarding the operational effectiveness of these processes has arisen. Design effectiveness for all processes is present, both in the interviews and in the underlying documentation provided by the case study organizations. Operational effectiveness of processes has been a topic of discussion and multiple interviewees have expressed doubt on operational effectiveness of several processes. Particularly complex processes like calculating true costs of development and determining the real total cost of ownership are experienced as challenging by organizations, in spite of being able to exercise (IT) budget control or chargeback arrangements. A similar observation is made with

In case only the practices are depicted that are identified in this research as being specific for Bimodal IT, the picture becomes even more clear, as can be observed in figure 15: Bimodal IT governance practices, patterns and observations - II. In this overview the increasing presence of these Bimodal IT specific archetypes are increasingly moving towards a full digital transformation is quite clear. The only dissonant is BGP2 that is noticed in organization A (archetype 1). This can be explained by going back to the phenomenon already mentioned when discussing the structures: an attempt to create a governing body to discuss the portfolio and set priorities according to business priorities and aligning business and IT was made but proved to be unreachable due to lack of knowledge across business domains. The consequence was that this governing body was once again split into business specific elements, hereby enabling decision making for specific areas, but losing the overall holistic element.

figure 15: Bimodal IT governance practices, patterns and observations - II

business priorities and aligning business and IT was made but proved to be unreachable due to lack of knowledge across business domains. The consequence was that this governing body was once again split into business specific elements, hereby enabling decision making for specific areas, but losing the overall holistic element.

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5 Conclusions and recommendations

In this chapter the research questions are answered. Next, conclusions are drawn from the answers and the analysis and corresponding recommendations are formulated. Also, the research project as a whole is assessed and noteworthy observations and uncovered issues are identified. Likewise, recommendations are formulated.

5.1 Answering research questions

From the substantiated concepts as characterized in the theoretical framework and the description and analysis of the research in the previous chapter it is now possible to answer the supporting questions to the main research question.

Supporting question 1 – What is governance of IT?

Combining the results from the theory in chapter 3 and the results from research, it has become clear that governance of IT is based on the presence, deployment and tailored quality of SPRM's in an organization. As mentioned in the definition from Van Grembergen and De Haes (Grembergen & Haes, 2015), executive management (Dutch: raad van bestuur) and the board of directors (Dutch: raad van commissarissen) play an essential role in the selection, prioritization and adaption of these SPRM's. However, to be able to identify, select and implement these SPRM's, specific knowledge is required, both at executive level and in the organization. This knowledge, that can be characterized as a combination of both IT- and business savviness, as awareness of the potential of technology and the ability to grasp the impact of technology on the primary and secondary processes in an organization is currently not commonly present in organizations. Summarizing, we propose to add these elements to the current definition of enterprise governance of IT:

Enterprise Governance of IT is an integral part of corporate governance, exercised by the Board, overseeing the definition and implementation of processes, structures and relational mechanisms, ***skillfully identified and chosen taking into account both the level of digitalization the organization has and can absorb, and the level of business- and IT-savviness that is present in the organization,*** that enable both business and IT people to execute their responsibilities in support of business/IT alignment and the creation of business value from IT-enabled business investments

Supporting question 2 – Which archetypes exist and how can they be distinguished?

Bimodal IT and its intermediate appearances (different archetypes) can be considered stepping stones on the road towards digital transformation. From scientific literature analysis it is clear five different archetypes of Bimodal IT can be distinguished, according to table 9: Five archetypes of Bimodal IT that can be seen below. As far as the term bimodal is concerned, it suffices to state that regardless of which exact term is used (see table 2 for detailed descriptions), bimodality is related to having two different heartbeats for different activities in developing, operating and creating value through technology.

5 different archetypes of Bimodal IT have been identified in scientific research:	
<p>Archetype 1</p>	<p>Traditional IT with bimodal development processes. Bimodality is limited to the development process, within traditional waterfall projects. All architecture, testing and operation processes but also other business management processes, continue to use the waterfall methodology.</p>
<p>Archetype 2</p>	<p>Traditional IT with Agile IT Outsourcing. Partly outsourced IT organization. Some projects are outsourced or executed together with business units. Outsourcing contracts and agreements must be made. Within the organization an internal project steering committee must be installed to manage both mode 1 (slow internal IT) and mode 2 (fast external IT). Business units are seen as “customers of IT”.</p>
<p>Archetype 3</p>	<p>Bimodal Sourcing IT. The organization is outsourcing 1 or even 2 bimodal modes, on a Client - Supplier basis or as an Internal Project Organization with corporate IT as a project manager and one or more outsourcing partners. Project managers are internally supplied and per project is decided on the used methodology (mode1/2). Budgets are controlled per project and project managers must be able to run projects in both modes. Business-IT alignment lies with individual project managers and with the steering committee. One or more partners deliver the skilled teams. A PMO provides the alignment across the projects that run in the organization.</p>
<p>Archetype 4</p>	<p>Bimodal IT. Delivery modes are separated, regarding structures and processes. Mode 1, traditional IT, led by the CIO, mainly functionally structured. Mode 2, Agile IT, led by the CDO, separate organization, separate processes, small teams, focuses on fast delivery of business outcomes. Scrum, a product owner, scrum master and DevOps are commonly used.</p>
<p>Archetype 5</p>	<p>Agile IT. Internal unimodal agile IT organization, small autonomous interdisciplinary teams, responsible for requirements, development, operations but also quality and assurance. Agile teams are responsible for team composition, decision structures and overall team mission. Alignment with business is provided by the product owner who is part of the Scrum team. Business Unit managers exist in a coaching capacity for teams. Steering and determination at company level is more or less traditional, Business and IT organized together in Digital Business Units</p>

table 9: Five archetypes of Bimodal IT

Supporting question 3 – Which specific structures, processes and relational mechanisms can be identified in literature, pertaining to the defined bimodal archetypes?

Across papers from scientific publications and whitepapers, publications and consulting research from leading consulting firms a total of 175 SPRM’s were identified in this research (Appendix H – Complete list of all SPRM’s found in literature). The research has aggregated these SPRM’s into 36 bimodal governance practices (Appendix K – SPRM distribution across Bimodal governance practices). Of these a total of 8 practices was found to be specific for Bimodal IT (Appendix I – Bimodal IT governance practices including literature reference).

The total overview is visualized in Appendix L – SPRM mapping. Summarizing the following table is relevant when answering this supporting question:

Practice type	Description
Generic governance practices (33)	33 practices, divided over 12 structures, 11 processes and 10 relational mechanisms as defined by Van Grembergen and De Haes (Grembergen & Haes, 2015)
Bimodal governance practices (36)	36 practices, aggregated from 175 SPRM's identified from various literature, 27 out of 33 generic governance practices and 8 specific practices for Bimodal IT (some, but not all of which are attributed to more than 1 generic practice, hence not 35).
Bimodal IT specific practices (8)	8 practices, consolidated out of the 175 SPRM's from various literature and mapped on archetype. 4 practices can be referenced to scientific research, 4 practices identified solely on this research project.

table 10: SPRM pertaining to bimodal archetypes

Supporting question 4 – In which way do the different archetypes contribute to the realization of governance of Bimodal IT?

The different bimodal archetypes can be considered stepping stones on the road towards digital transformation. In this context, they can be used as guiding posts on the road that organizations must walk in this process. Being aware of the current archetype an organization has, they may be used as pointer for next steps. These steps can be an indication that before certain decisions can come into effect other actions or activities must be started, like education, the establishment of specific roles, adding or insourcing specific skills and competencies etc. etc. In general, the statement can be made that different archetypes show resemblance with a five-point maturity scale, that could be used as a roadmap for organizations evolving towards full digital transformation. First steps in creating such a roadmap have already been described for organizations that want to move from a traditional IT organization to Bimodal IT (Haffke et al., 2017a). Creating a roadmap across the different archetypes to full digital transformation could be a next step in this sequence.

Central research question – How do organizations govern their IT in a bimodal archetype?

First and foremost, the observation can be made that governance of IT is, also in a bimodal archetype, just that: governance of IT. Exercising this governance remains a responsibility of the board and a part of corporate governance, albeit specific knowledge and skills are required in the board and throughout the organization. The use of structures, processes and relational mechanisms in order to be able to govern remains unchanged. However, for bimodal organizations a number of specific SPRM-practices are identified. Recognizing these and being aware of their spread and occurrence across the different archetypes supports the appropriate governance of an organization. Ultimately, the answer to the question of how organizations govern their IT in a bimodal archetype is:

Through the adoption of structures, processes and relational mechanisms that are suitable and tailored for bimodal environments.

Suitable meaning the SPRM's are relevant for the specific archetype an organization (currently) has, with a spread as pictured in Appendix B – SPRM, plot on Organization. Tailored should be interpreted as keeping aligned to the inherently dynamic state of organizations, meaning the continuous (small) changes required to address the organizations context, industry type, volumes, market, physical environment, culture etc. etc.

5.2 Conclusions

From the answers to the research questions and the analysis several observations can be made.

A cautious conclusion can be drawn that moving from bimodal archetype 1 to archetype 5 there appears to be a gradual increase in digitalization of organizations. This bears the possibility to be converted into a maturity model with intermediate steps moving from traditional IT towards full digital transformation. Notable here is that by no means embarking on a change from traditional IT to Bimodal IT means there is an obligation to transform to fully digitalized, the lead indicator should always be the requirements of the organization.

The strong presence of processes across all organizations is somewhat surprising, given their relative perceived difficulty to implement (see table 7: 33 EGIT practices and their perceived effectiveness and ease of implementation). Being present in documentation and being discussed as active process during interviews, no discussion exists regarding the design effectiveness of processes. However, some doubts have arisen towards their operational effectiveness.

The knowledge required to be able to identify, tailor and implement specific bimodal SPRM's is not available across all employees, but only with individuals. Both at executive level and throughout organizations. On a practical level, some organizations solve this by insourcing specific knowledge. However, obtaining both business- and IT-savviness from top to bottom is challenging, as can be observed from specific Bimodal IT practices BGS1, BGS2 and also even BGR2 (see Appendix J). A statement can be made that the general state of the majority of employees across all levels in organizations with regard to digital transformation, bimodality and their associated knowledge areas varies between unconsciously incompetent and consciously incompetent.

Identification of 8 practices that are specific for Bimodal IT has been performed in this research project. Further definition and elaboration of these practices is recommended.

No evidence was found, nor discussed in interviews of informal joint activities of (senior) managers from both IT and business side of the organization discuss general topics without specific agenda. In the list of SPRM's this is listed as being perceived quite easy to implement (rank 5 out of 33), whilst being relatively effective (rank 12 out of 33).

Funding of digitizing activities, especially in more advanced bimodal archetypes (archetype 4,5) requires a different type of financial resource allocation than the traditional budget cycle or the traditional funding method of projects (presenting a business case leads to the allocation of a budget) permits.

Moving towards digitalization, including the increasing adoption of mode 2 way of working for all IT related activities in an organization logically means that decision-making processes must follow. This requires a more agile way of decision making. Currently the decision-making processes in organizations are still mostly top down decision-making and focus on traditional business IT alignment (Horlach & Drews, 2018), as confirmed by the latest scientific research on this subject. A decision-making balance between authority embedded in governance structuration and operational autonomy needs to be sought.

For an organization that aspires to be Bimodal IT, the balance between mode 1 and mode 2 activities has to shift towards higher volumes of mode 2. Currently the observed volumes of mode 2 activities are only the dominating way of working in a minority of organizations. As long as mode 1 operations are predominantly present, real adoption of mode 2 cannot be achieved.

Presence of (bimodal) governance practices is strong in development and in business areas of organizations. In (IT) operations this presence is low. Possible causes are the traditional focus of organizations on funding and financial accounting. This leads to either governance focus on development, managing business cases and getting requirements that should yield a (financial) benefit. Or, alternatively, to a focus on business side, where the value (financial benefit) is to be created. The supporting organizational level of (IT) operations is too little involved and taken too much for granted.

Above findings are summarized in table 11: Case study research findings

ID	Finding	Description
1	Roadmap potential	Archetypes 1-5 appear to be of increasing maturity. Possibility for logical steps moving from archetype 1 → archetype 5.
2	Processes operational effectiveness	Presence of processes is strong; design effectiveness of processes can be verified. Operational effectiveness of processes is suspected to lag.
3	Knowledge gap	Knowledge on Bimodal IT, SPRM's and application for enterprise governance of IT not readily available across organizations. Current state from unconsciously to consciously incompetent.
4	Specific practices for Bimodal IT	Eight practices have been identified, but further definition and elaboration of these practices is recommended.
5	Informal meetings	In spite of relative little effort yielding good results, no informal meetings between business and IT senior management are organized.
6	Specific bimodal funding	Funding of Bimodal IT, especially for more advanced types fundamentally different from traditional funding of IT
7	Decision-making processes	Traditional top-down decision making not aligned with mode 2 operation of IT
8	Mode 1 volume increase	Traditional mode 1 operation too predominantly present impede progressing towards digitization
9	Lack of operational focus	Too much governance focus on the development and business areas, leaving (IT) operations getting too little attention.

table 11: Case study research findings

5.3 Recommendations

In this paragraph the recommendations for the research findings are given, based on the findings recorded in the previous section. Also, for each recommendation at least two suggestions are given how the (effect of a) recommendation can be measured.

ID	Finding	Description	Recommendation	Measurement suggestion
1	Roadmap potential	Archetypes 1-5 appear to be of increasing maturity. Possibility for logical steps moving from archetype 1 → archetype 5.	Further research identifying maturity levels for Bimodal IT. Possibly converting this into a roadmap for organizations towards digital transformation	Identified maturity stages for Bimodal IT # organizations with identified Bimodal IT stage # organizations successfully digitized
2	Processes operational effectiveness	Presence of processes is strong; design effectiveness of processes can be verified. Operational effectiveness of processes is suspected to lag.	Conduct regular (annual) independent audit and/or maturity assessment on selected processes	Increase in process maturity level Reduction in # audit findings for selected processes

ID	Finding	Description	Recommendation	Measurement suggestion
3	Knowledge gap	Knowledge on Bimodal IT, SPRM's and application for enterprise governance of IT not readily available across organizations. Current state from unconsciously to consciously incompetent.	Issue awareness campaigns on governance. Educate key staff on governance of IT. <u>Proposal</u> to extend EGIT definition with: "skillfully identified and chosen taking into account both the level of digitalization the organization has and can absorb, and the level of business- and IT-savviness that is present in the organization"	# and/or % increase in staff with diploma or certificate for governance Reduction in # audit findings on governance Companywide adoption of governance frameworks like COBIT5
4	Specific practices for Bimodal IT	Eight practices have been identified, but further definition and elaboration of these practices is recommended.	Further research and definition of specific Bimodal IT practices e.g. through Delphi research	# increase in defined and useable criteria for Bimodal IT governance / maturity # citations for specific Bimodal IT criteria in various literature
5	Informal meetings	In spite of relative little effort yielding good results, no informal meetings between business and IT senior management are organized.	Organize regular informal meetings for senior management without agenda.	# informal meetings actually held % increase of participants to informal events
6	Specific bimodal funding	Funding of Bimodal IT, especially for more advanced archetypes is fundamentally different from traditional funding of IT	Develop flexible funding principles for mode 2 activities Review and adaptation of traditional budget cycle in organization (intermediate measure) Transform from yearly cycle to quarterly cycle for allocating budgets to mode 2 activities	# of mode 2 activities / projects funded outside regular budget cycle % or # of (new) products / services where transparent benefit (value) management report is created and includes non-viable (discarded) projects / ideas (full development cost made transparent)
7	Decision-making processes	Traditional top-down decision making not aligned with mode 2 operation of IT	Allocate specific autonomy in mode 2 teams Develop decision-making process with flexible balance between top-down structuration and team autonomy	# decisions made in teams differing from original management directive that were supported in hindsight

ID	Finding	Description	Recommendation	Measurement suggestion
8	Mode 1 volume increase	Traditional mode 1 operation too predominantly present impede progressing towards digitization	Freeze mode 1 developments increasing legacy. Transform mode 1 actively to mode 2, reducing mode 1 operations volume compared to mode 2.	% increase in teams with a true business product owner leading the team % annual / quarterly reduction in systems of record % increase in agile teams as part of staff
9	Lack of operational focus	Too much governance focus on the development and business areas, leaving (IT) operations getting too little attention.	Job rotation between development and operational roles Co-location of development and operations teams Integration of operations activities in development teams (DevOps)	Increase in # practices present in operations # developers assigned operations tasks # system administrators members of development project teams

table 12: Case study research recommendations

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7 Appendices

7.1 Appendix A – Five bimodal archetypes

Archetype 1: Traditional IT with bimodal development

Archetype 2: Traditional IT with Agile IT Outsourcing

Archetype 3: Bimodal Sourcing with or without project management

Archetype 4: Bimodal IT with or without DBU's

Archetype 5: Agile IT with or without DBU's

7.2 Appendix B – SPRM, plot on Organization

Explanation of signs:

- Essential (Bimodal) SPRM, found both in literature analysis and case organizations
- Essential (Bimodal) SPRM, found both in literature analysis (but not for this archetype!) and case organizations
- (Bimodal) SPRM, found both in literature analysis and case organizations
- (Bimodal) SPRM, found both in literature analysis (but not for this archetype!) and case organizations
- Essential (Bimodal) SPRM, found in literature analysis but not present in case organizations
- (Bimodal) SPRM, found in literature analysis but not present in case organizations

7.3 Appendix C – List of requested documents

Documents required for thesis research – bimodal IT

As discussed during your interview, we would like to receive written documentation describing or related to how your organization is governing the bimodal archetype that you are running.

We would like to receive following documents (or similar, if existing) from you:

- IT Strategy document
 - How is IT supporting the achievement of Business goals / strategy?
- IT Policy document
 - What are the “rules of the game” when you want to play with IT?
- Architecture standards / policy document
 - Outlining the framework of basic IT choices.
- Orgchart (overall + IT organization)
 - Organizational description, departments, teams.
- Project management standard
 - Do you use a standard (Prince2, PMBoK), a mix, a tailored solution?
- IT principles document
 - Giving pointers like e.g.: “IT is the exclusive provider of IT Services. Outsourcing is always organized in joint partnership between business and IT” or “IT is pro-actively engaged in reviewing and designing efficient business processes”.
- Any other documents that you deem relevant for our research

Together with the input from the interview(s) in your organization, we will use the documentation solely to identify & validate SPRM’s (Structures, Processes and Relational Mechanisms) pertaining to the archetype of bimodal that your organization is deploying.

7.4 Appendix D – Introduction for interviews

Introduction for research interview – bimodal IT

As discussed with you previously, you will be interviewed about the way your company is managing the 2 different speeds of running IT in your organization. This is part of master thesis research answering the (central research) question:

“How do organizations govern their IT in a bimodal archetype?”

5 different archetypes of bimodal have been identified in scientific research:	
<p>Archetype 1</p>	<p>Traditional IT with bimodal development processes. Bimodality is limited to the development process, within traditional waterfall projects. All architecture, testing and operation processes but also other business management processes, continue to use the waterfall methodology.</p>
<p>Archetype 2</p>	<p>Traditional IT with Agile IT Outsourcing. Partly outsourced IT organization. Some projects are outsourced or executed together with business units. Outsourcing contracts and agreements must be made. Within the organization an internal project steering committee must be installed to manage both mode 1 (slow internal IT) and mode 2 (fast external IT). Business units are seen as “customers of IT”.</p>
<p>Archetype 3</p>	<p>Bimodal Sourcing IT. The organization is outsourcing 1 or even 2 bimodal modes, on a Client - Supplier basis or as an Internal Project Organization with corporate IT as a project manager and one or more outsourcing partners. Project managers are internally supplied and per project is decided on the used methodology (mode1/2). Budgets are controlled per project and project managers must be able to run projects in both modes. Business-IT alignment lies with individual project managers and with the steering committee. One or more partners deliver the skilled teams. A PMO provides the alignment across the projects that run in the organization.</p>
<p>Archetype 4</p>	<p>Bimodal IT. Delivery modes are separated, regarding structures and processes. Mode 1, traditional IT, led by the CIO, mainly functionally structured. Mode 2, Agile IT, led by the CDO, separate organization, separate processes, small teams, focuses on fast delivery of business outcomes. Scrum, a product owner, scrum master and DevOps are commonly used.</p>
<p>Archetype 5</p>	<p>Agile IT. Internal unimodal agile IT organization, small autonomous interdisciplinary teams, responsible for requirements, development, operations but also quality and assurance. Agile teams are responsible for team composition, decision structures and overall team mission. Alignment with business is provided by the product owner who is part of the Scrum team. Business Unit managers exist in a coaching capacity for teams. Steering and determination at company level is more or less traditional, Business and IT organized together in Digital Business Units</p>

We seek to identify which archetype fits your organization. Also, which structures, processes and relational mechanisms are in use in your organization to manage this archetype.

Structures: e.g. an IT steering committee, an architecture board or is the CIO member of the board of directors.

Processes: e.g. portfolio management, release management, budget control (financial management)

Relational Mechanisms: e.g. co-location (IT and business), job rotation, joint events

7.5 Appendix E – Operationalization

Elements	How to research	Research method
Governance	What is the definition of governance? What are elements that construct governance?	Content analysis
Bimodal IT	What is Bimodal IT? What are manifestations of Bimodal IT?	Content analysis, interviews
SPRM's	See division below	
Structures	What are structures in relation to governance of IT? Which structures are essential for governance of IT? Which structures are specific for Bimodal IT?	Content analysis, interviews
Processes	What are processes in relation to governance of IT? Which processes are essential for governance of IT? Which processes are specific for Bimodal IT?	Content analysis, interviews
Relational Mechanisms	What are relational mechanisms in relation to governance of IT? Which relational mechanisms are essential for governance of IT? Which relational mechanisms are specific for Bimodal IT?	Content analysis, interviews

7.6 Appendix F – Interview questions

Semi-structured interview questions for thesis research – bimodal IT

Introduction:

- Part of master thesis research into practical applications of bimodal IT. Researching how this is governed in organizations in practice.
- Expected interview time is 60-90 minutes
- Results will be published anonymized in the thesis, subject to review by AMS exam committee only
- Additional physical documentation at the end of this interview will be requested

Rules of the game:

- Your name will not be used
- There are no correct / incorrect answers, it's research
- A formal tone of questioning may be used, this is for coding reasons
- The interviewer is not a participant, just stands on the sideline
- Is it ok to record the interview?
- (for interviewer) Ask examples regularly!

Questions:

Q – on structures

1. Which archetype of bimodal as described in the introduction fits your company?
2. To whom does the CIO report? (if CxO, is CIO member of the BoD)
3. Is there an IT strategy committee/council, if yes, who are the members?
4. How / who decides on IT investments?
5. How / who decides on IT policies & architecture?
6. How are your suppliers managed?
7. How are projects managed and organized and how are decisions made?
8. Which development methodologies do you use?
9. Is there an IT roadmap?

Q – on processes

1. Are there best practices/standards in use? (ITIL, ISO 20000, ISO27000, ISO38500, COBIT, Prince2, PMP/PMI, SAFe, COSO-ERM, TOGAF, MoR, Agile, Scrum, LEAN, DevOps, ... others?)
2. What is the estimated maturity (on a 5 level scale) of processes/organization?
3. Is portfolio management implemented and formally managed?
4. Is IT Strategy formally reviewed and updated?
5. Is there a formal project methodology?
6. Are any formal "IT principles" established (e.g. IT is the exclusive provider of IT services. Outsourcing always organized in joint partnership between Business & IT).
7. How is the IT Budget controlled & managed?

Q – on relational mechanisms

1. IT Leadership – how well is IT able to articulate it's added value to (business) managers throughout the organization in such a way that they understand and cooperate?
2. Is leading by example across the organization a normal practice?
3. Are there any areas / examples where IT and business employees are working together on a daily basis?
4. Is "IT-savviness" a topic when formulating skills matrices in the business? (How, example)
5. Is "Business-savviness" a topic when formulating skills matrices in the IT? (How, example)

Completion:

- Give a short summary of the interview. Opportunity for interviewee to return or change answer for certain topics
- Ask the interviewee if they are satisfied. Ask for feedback / tips.

7.7 Appendix G – 33 EGIT practices

Minimum	Index	IT governance practice	Definition
Y	S1	IT strategy committee at level of board of directors	Committee at level of board of directors to ensure IT is regular agenda item and reporting issue for the board of directors
N	S2	IT expertise at level of board of directors	Members of the board of directors have expertise and experience regarding the value and risk of IT
N	S3	(IT) audit committee at level of board of directors	Independent committee at level of board of directors overseeing (IT) assurance activities
Y	S4	CIO on executive committee	CIO is a full member of the executive committee
Y	S5	CIO (Chief Information Officer) reporting to CEO (Chief Executive Officer) and/or COO (Chief Operational Officer)	CIO has a direct reporting line to the CEO and/or COO
Y	S6	IT steering committee (IT investment evaluation / prioritisation at executive / senior management level)	Steering committee at executive or senior management level responsible for determining business priorities in IT investments.
N	S7	IT governance function / officer	Function in the organisation responsible for promoting, driving and managing IT governance processes
N	S8	Security / compliance / risk officer	Function responsible for security, compliance and/or risk, which possibly impacts IT
Y	S9	IT project steering committee	Steering committee composed of business and IT people focusing on prioritising and managing IT projects
N	S10	IT security steering committee	Steering committee composed of business and IT people focusing on IT related risks and security issues
N	S11	Architecture steering committee	Committee composed of business and IT people providing architecture guidelines and advise on their applications.
N	S12	Integration of governance/alignment tasks in roles & responsibilities	Documented roles & responsibilities include governance/alignment tasks for business and IT people (cf. Weill)
Y	P1	Strategic information systems planning	Formal process to define and update the IT strategy
N	P2	IT performance measurement (e.g. IT balanced scorecard)	IT performance measurement in domains of corporate contribution, user orientation, operational excellence and future orientation
Y	P3	Portfolio management (incl. business cases, information economics, ROI, payback)	Prioritisation process for IT investments and projects in which business and IT is involved (incl. business cases)
N	P4	Charge back arrangements - total cost of ownership (e.g. activity based costing)	Methodology to charge back IT costs to business units, to enable an understanding of the total cost of ownership
N	P5	Service level agreements	Formal agreements between business and IT about IT development projects or IT operations
N	P6	IT governance framework COBIT	Process based IT governance and control framework
N	P7	IT governance assurance and self-assessment	Regular self-assessments or independent assurance activities on the governance and control over IT
Y	P8	Project governance / management methodologies	Processes and methodologies to govern and manage IT projects
Y	P9	IT budget control and reporting	Processes to control and report upon budgets of IT investments and projects
N	P10	Benefits management and reporting	Processes to monitor the planned business benefits during and after implementation of the IT investments / projects.
N	P11	COSO / ERM	Framework for internal control
N	R1	Job-rotation	IT staff working in the business units and business people working in IT
N	R2	Co-location	Physically locating business and IT people close to each other
N	R3	Cross-training	Training business people about IT and/or training IT people about business
N	R4	Knowledge management (on IT governance)	Systems (intranet, ...) to share and distribute knowledge about IT governance framework, responsibilities, tasks, etc.
N	R5	Business/IT account management	Bridging the gap between business and IT by means of account managers who act as in-between
N	R6	Senior business and IT management acting as "partners"	Executive / senior management giving the good example
N	R7	Informal meetings between business and IT executive/ senior management	Informal meetings, with no agenda, where business and IT senior management talk about general activities, directions, etc. (e.g. during informal lunches)
Y	R8	IT leadership	Ability of CIO or similar role to articulate a vision for IT's role in the company and ensure that this vision is clearly understood by managers throughout the organisation
N	R9	Corporate internal communication addressing IT on a regular basis	Internal corporate communication regularly addresses general IT issues.
N	R10	IT governance awareness campaigns	Campaigns to explain to business and IT people the need for IT governance

7.8 Appendix H – Complete list of all SPRM’s found in literature

Bimodal IT Governance						
Item	ID	Archetype	Bimodal Governance Practice	SPRM description	Reference	36 governance practices used in this research
Relational Mechanism	1	1	Development of IT- and Business-Convergence in the organization (Horlach, 2018)	Knowledge Sharing by developers during handover [01]	(Horlach et al., 2017a)	Y
Relational Mechanism	2	1	IT originating body taking the lead in bidirectional collaboration between Business and IT to enable convergence (Horlach 2018)	Business-IT alignment, Project Mgt for Agile B-IT alignment [02]	(Horlach et al., 2017a)	Y
Structures	3	2,3,4,5		IT Steering Committee (traditional) for Mode 1 and Mode 2 [03];[10];[22]	(Horlach et al., 2017a)	Y
Structures	4	2,3,4		IT Steering Committee (traditional) for Outsourced projects by contracts & agreements [04];[11]	(Horlach et al., 2017a)	Y
Processes	5	1,2,3,4,5		IT Budget Control and Reporting, per Business project [05], [43]; [19]	(Horlach et al., 2017a)	Y
Processes	6	2		Portfolio Management (BC, ROI, Information Economics, Value creation). Complex Portfolio management. IT is responsible for condensing the separate portfolio's into one overall portfolio [06]	(Horlach et al., 2017a)	Y
Processes	7	2		Business/IT alignment, by tuning IT portfolio to Business needs (via requirements engineering) aka Portfolio Mgt[07]	(Horlach et al., 2017a)	Y
Processes	8	2		Outsourcing to reduce time to market (adaptive) [08];	(Horlach et al., 2017a), (Mingay, Mesaglio, & Scott, 2016)	Y
Relational Mechanism	9	2	Development of IT- and Business-Convergence in the organization (Horlach, 2018)	Co-location of project team within company [09]	(Horlach et al., 2017a)	Y
Structures	10	3		IT Steering Committee (traditional) for Mode 1 and Mode 2 [03];[10];[22]	(Horlach et al., 2017a)	
Structures	11	3		IT Steering Committee (traditional) for Outsourced projects by contracts & agreements [04];[11]	(Horlach et al., 2017a)	
Relational Mechanism	12	3	IT originating body taking the lead in bidirectional collaboration between Business and IT to enable convergence (Horlach 2018)	Business/IT alignment, through requirements engineering [12]	(Horlach et al., 2017a)	
Relational Mechanism	13	3	Development of IT- and Business-Convergence in the organization (Horlach, 2018)	Direct interaction among project managers is ensured by locally centralizing all people in a department with fixed workplaces. [13]	(Horlach et al., 2017a)	
Relational Mechanism	14	3	IT originating body taking the lead in bidirectional collaboration between Business and IT to enable convergence (Horlach 2018)	Business/IT alignment, through individual project managers [14]	(Horlach et al., 2017a)	
Structures	15	3		IT Steering Committee traditional for Business/IT alignment [15]	(Horlach et al., 2017a)	
Relational Mechanism	16	3,4,5	Development of IT- and Business-Convergence in the organization (Horlach, 2018)	Outsourcing (adaptive) project teams [16]; Outsourcing partners deliver solely the skilled teams	(Horlach et al., 2017a), (Mingay, Mesaglio, & Scott, 2016)	
Relational Mechanism	17	3	IT originating body taking the lead in bidirectional collaboration between Business and IT to enable convergence (Horlach 2018)	Business/IT alignment, through project management office. Can be enhanced with Business role (program manager) [17]	(Horlach et al., 2017a)	
Processes	18	3	Agile practices used as replacement of traditional project management techniques and methods	Traditional (IT) program- and Project Management methodology, mixed with Agile project management (dual PM's) [18]; [34]	(Horlach et al., 2017a)	Y
Processes	19	3		Separate IT Budget Control and Reporting, per Agile project [19], [43]; [5]	(Horlach et al., 2017a)	
Processes	20	3		Portfolio Management (BC, ROI, Information Economics, Value creation), project based [20]	(Horlach et al., 2017a)	
Structures	21	4,5	Digital expertise and clear division of accountabilities at executive level between exploitation and exploration collaborating towards business and IT convergence	Existence of a CDO function [21], CIO and CDO [21] on CxO level and reporting to CEO/COO	(Horlach et al., 2017a)	Y
Structures	22	4		IT Steering Committee (traditional) for Mode 1 and Mode 2 [03];[10];[22]	(Horlach et al., 2017a)	
Structures	23	4		IT Steering Committee traditional for interaction with Business [23]	(Horlach et al., 2017a)	
Processes	24	4	Agile practices used as replacement of traditional project management techniques and methods	Agile (IT) program- and Project Management methodology [24]	(Horlach et al., 2017a)	
Structures	25	4,5		Product Owner, Scrum Master [25]	(Horlach et al., 2017a)	Y
Processes	26	4	Agile practices used as replacement of traditional project management techniques and methods	Framework SAFE [26], [80]	(Leffingwell, 2017)	
Processes	27	4		Separate IT Budget Control and Reporting for mode 1 and mode 2 [27], or funding per product/team [82]; [NOOT: dit geldt niet alleen hiervoor, maar voor ALLE structuren & processen]	(Horlach et al., 2017a)	
Relational Mechanism	28	4	IT originating body taking the lead in bidirectional collaboration between Business and IT to enable convergence (Horlach 2018)	Business/IT alignment due to widely adapted Agile and thus corporation between IT and Business [28]	(Horlach et al., 2017a)	
Relational Mechanism	29	4		Business/IT alignment due to corporation between CIO and CDO [29]	(Horlach et al., 2017a), (Hafke, Kalgovas, & Benlian, 2016)	Y
Processes	30	4		Sourcing mainly on technical expertise [30]	(Horlach et al., 2017a)	
Structures	31	5		Business/IT Steering Committee per DBU (Investments, Prioritization, Projects, Architecture and Security) [31]	(Horlach et al., 2017a)	
Structures	32	5	Digital expertise and clear division of accountabilities at executive level between exploitation and exploration collaborating towards business and IT convergence	CIO on CxO level, responsible for Agile Delivery [32]	(Horlach et al., 2017a)	
Processes	33	5	Business integration practices to enable converging business and IT in structure and strategy (Horlach 2018)	Portfolio Mgt with Business (BC, ROI, Information Economics, Value creation) [60] [33], [61]	(Horlach et al., 2017a)	Y
Processes	34	5	Agile practices used as replacement of traditional project management techniques and methods	Project Management methodology [34] [18]	(Horlach et al., 2017a)	
Structures	35	5		Product Owner is leading the team that is responsible for Method choosing, staffing, mission etc. is a team responsibility [35];[39]	(Horlach et al., 2017a)	
Processes	36	5		Business / IT Budget Control and Reporting based on products [36]	(Horlach et al., 2017a)	
Relational Mechanism	37	5	Development of IT- and Business-Convergence in the organization (Horlach, 2018)	Knowledge Sharing is common, due to use frameworks like Spotify (Guilds) [37]	(Kniberg Henrik; Ivarsson Anders, 2012)	
Relational Mechanism	38	5		Managers for coaching teams [38]	(Horlach et al., 2017a)	Y
Structures	39	5		Product Owner is leading the team that is responsible for Method choosing, staffing, mission etc. is a team responsibility [35];[39]	(Horlach et al., 2017a)	
Relational Mechanism	40	5	Development of IT- and Business-Convergence in the organization (Horlach, 2018)	Dedicated Supervisor for personnel development [40]	(Horlach et al., 2017a)	
Structures	41	2,3,4		Architecture Review Board [41]	(MacDorman & Gulzar, 2017)	Y
Processes	42	2,3		Asset Management [42]	(MacDorman & Gulzar, 2017)	
Processes	43	2,3		Separate IT Budget Control and Reporting, per Agile project [19], [43]; [5]	(MacDorman & Gulzar, 2017)	
Structures	44	4		IT Steering Committee (BC → projects) [44]	(MacDorman & Gulzar, 2017)	
Processes	45	4		Chargeback arrangements [45]	(MacDorman & Gulzar, 2017)	Y
Structures	46	4		Investment Committee [46]	(MacDorman & Gulzar, 2017)	
Structures	47	4,5		IT Business/ Executive council [47]	(MacDorman & Gulzar, 2017)	Y
Structures	48	4		IT Leadership committee [48]	(MacDorman & Gulzar, 2017)	
Processes	49	4		Program Management Office [49]	(MacDorman & Gulzar, 2017)	Y
Structures	50	4		Project Portfolio Board [50]	(MacDorman & Gulzar, 2017)	
Structures	51	4		Risk Advisory Board [51]	(MacDorman & Gulzar, 2017)	Y
Structures	52	4		Sponsor committee [52]	(MacDorman & Gulzar, 2017)	
Structures	53	4		Technical [53] Steering committee (see Architecture Board)	(MacDorman & Gulzar, 2017)	
Processes	54	4	Agile practices used as replacement of traditional project management techniques and methods	User Group [54] Steering committee. In existence a structure, logged as process due to the function in replacing/supporting traditional Project Steering in Agile environments	(MacDorman & Gulzar, 2017)	
Relational Mechanism	55	4	IT originating body taking the lead in bidirectional collaboration between Business and IT to enable convergence (Horlach 2018)	Business-IT Relation manager [55];[17]	(MacDorman & Gulzar, 2017)	

Bimodal IT Governance						
Item	ID	Archetype	Bimodal Governance Practice	SPRM description	Reference	36 governance practices used in this research
Relational Mechanism	56	4	IT originating body taking the lead in bidirectional collaboration between Business and IT to enable convergence (Horlach 2018)	(Business) Sponsor [56]; (aka Product Owner) [65]; [83]	(MacDorman & Gulzar, 2017)	
Processes	57	5	Agile practices used as replacement of traditional project management techniques and methods	Backlog [57]	(MacDorman & Gulzar, 2017)	
Processes	58	5	Agile practices used as replacement of traditional project management techniques and methods	Sprint [58]	(MacDorman & Gulzar, 2017)	
Processes	59	5	Agile practices used as replacement of traditional project management techniques and methods	User Stories [59]	(MacDorman & Gulzar, 2017)	
Processes	60	5		Portfolio Mgt with Business (BC, ROI, Information Economics, Value creation [60]) [33], [61]	(MacDorman & Gulzar, 2017)	
Processes	61	5		Portfolio Mgt with Business (BC, ROI, Information Economics, Value creation [60]) [33], [61]	(MacDorman & Gulzar, 2017)	
Processes	62	5	Agile practices used as replacement of traditional project management techniques and methods	Agile (IT) Program Management methodology [62]	(MacDorman & Gulzar, 2017)	
Processes	63	5	Agile practices used as replacement of traditional project management techniques and methods	Product Prototyping [63]	(MacDorman & Gulzar, 2017)	
Structures	64	4,5	Specific Agile roles in job structures and formal documentation of corresponding responsibilities	Design Authority [64]	(MacDorman & Gulzar, 2017)	Y
Structures	65	5	Specific Agile roles in job structures and formal documentation of corresponding responsibilities	Product Owner [65]; [56]; [83]	(MacDorman & Gulzar, 2017)	
Processes	66	1,2	Agile practices used as replacement of traditional project management techniques and methods	Iterative / Incremental Development & SAFe [66]	(Holz, 2017), (Mingay, Mesaglio, & Scott, 2016)	
Processes	67	3	Agile practices used as replacement of traditional project management techniques and methods	Extreme Programming XP [67]	(Holz, 2017)	
Processes	68	3	Agile practices used as replacement of traditional project management techniques and methods	Scrum [68]	(Holz, 2017)	
Processes	69	3	Agile practices used as replacement of traditional project management techniques and methods	DAD [69]	(Holz, 2017)	
Processes	70	4,5	Agile practices used as replacement of traditional project management techniques and methods	Kanban [70]	(Holz, 2017)	
Processes	71	4,5	Agile practices used as replacement of traditional project management techniques and methods	Scrumban [71]	(Holz, 2017)	
Processes	72	4,5	Agile practices used as replacement of traditional project management techniques and methods	Lean Startup [72]	(Holz, 2017)	
Processes	73	4,5	Agile practices used as replacement of traditional project management techniques and methods	LeSS [73]	(Holz, 2017)	
Processes	74	4,5	Agile practices used as replacement of traditional project management techniques and methods	Nexus [74]	(Holz, 2017)	
Processes	75	4	Business integration practices to enable converging business and IT in structure and strategy (Horlach 2018)	Bimodal Program- and Portfolio Mgt [75]	(Hanford, 2016)	
Processes	76	4	Business integration practices to enable converging business and IT in structure and strategy (Horlach 2018)	PPM building a Roadmap [76]	(Hanford, 2016)	
Structures	77	4,5		Multi disciplinary teams [77]	(Mingay, Mesaglio, & Scott, 2016)	
Relational Mechanism	78	4,5	Development of IT- and Business-Convergence in the organization (Horlach, 2018)	Workshops, Proof of Concepts and Demo's [78]	(Mingay, Mesaglio, & Scott, 2016)	Y
Relational Mechanism	79	4,5	Development of IT- and Business-Convergence in the organization (Horlach, 2018)	Job Rotation between Mode 1 and Mode 2 [79]	(Mingay, Mesaglio, & Scott, 2016)	Y
Processes	80	4,5	Agile practices used as replacement of traditional project management techniques and methods	Framework SAFe [26], [80]	(Leffingwell, 2017), (Mingay, Mesaglio, & Scott, 2016)	
Processes	81	4,5	Agile practices used as replacement of traditional project management techniques and methods	Focus on products, not projects [81]. Focus on organizational transition from project (short term, myopic, limited scope), to product (long term, resource efficiency)	(Mingay, Mesaglio, & Scott, 2016)	
Processes	82	4,5	Adapted funding principles tailored to rapid Agile delivery cycles	Separate IT Budget Control and Reporting for mode 1 and mode 2 [27], or funding per product/team [82]; Funding per product/team [82]	(Mingay, Mesaglio, & Scott, 2016)	Y
Relational Mechanism	83	4,5	IT originating body taking the lead in bidirectional collaboration between Business and IT to enable convergence (Horlach 2018)	Product Mgt [83] referring to role of (senior / chief) Product Owner [65]; [56]	(Mingay, Mesaglio, & Scott, 2016)	
Processes	84	4,5		Technology driven Product Mgt and Innovation Mgt [84]; (context of product mgt: long term, resource efficiency)	(Bayley & Shacklady, 2015), (Behar, Weber, & Simone, 2015), (Ram, 2017)	Y
Processes	85	4	Adapted funding principles tailored to rapid Agile delivery cycles	Venture Capital (funding) principle [85]	(Bayley & Shacklady, 2015), (Behar, Weber, & Simone, 2015), (Ram, 2017)	
Processes	86	4,5	Adapted funding principles tailored to rapid Agile delivery cycles	Flexible/dynamic decision and budget cycles [86]	(Bayley & Shacklady, 2015), (Behar, Weber, & Simone, 2015), (Ram, 2017)	
Processes	87	4,5	Agile practices used as replacement of traditional project management techniques and methods	Agile development [87]	(Bayley & Shacklady, 2015), (Behar, Weber, & Simone, 2015), (Ram, 2017)	
Processes	88	4,5	Agile practices used as replacement of traditional project management techniques and methods	DevOps [88]	(Bayley & Shacklady, 2015), (Behar, Weber, & Simone, 2015), (Ram, 2017)	
Processes	89	4,5		Transformational Architecture Mgt [89] (setting standards for release cadence enabling mode 1 and mode 2)	(Bayley & Shacklady, 2015), (Behar, Weber, & Simone, 2015), (Ram, 2017)	
Processes	90	4,5		Release Mgt [90]	(Bayley & Shacklady, 2015), (Behar, Weber, & Simone, 2015), (Ram, 2017)	
Processes	91	4,5		Service Broker age [91]; (related to supplier management & SIAM, choosing from available market options and quickly integrate)	(Bayley & Shacklady, 2015), (Behar, Weber, & Simone, 2015), (Ram, 2017)	
Structures	92	4,5	Specific Agile roles in job structures and formal documentation of corresponding responsibilities	Centralized Data & Analytics [92]	(Bayley & Shacklady, 2015), (Behar, Weber, & Simone, 2015), (Ram, 2017)	
Structures	93	4,5	Specific Agile roles in job structures and formal documentation of corresponding responsibilities	Centralized Customer Interaction [93]	(Bayley & Shacklady, 2015), (Behar, Weber, & Simone, 2015), (Ram, 2017)	
Structures	94	4,5	Specific Agile roles in job structures and formal documentation of corresponding responsibilities	Mobile Center of Excellence (App dev.) [94]	(Bayley & Shacklady, 2015), (Behar, Weber, & Simone, 2015), (Ram, 2017)	
Structures	95	4	Specific Agile roles in job structures and formal documentation of corresponding responsibilities	Agile Staff (initiate/promote culture) [95]	(Bayley & Shacklady, 2015), (Behar, Weber, & Simone, 2015), (Ram, 2017)	
Processes	96	4,5		Security Strategy [96]	(Bayley & Shacklady, 2015), (Behar, Weber, & Simone, 2015), (Ram, 2017)	Y
Processes	97	4,5		Security Governance [97]	(Bayley & Shacklady, 2015), (Behar, Weber, & Simone, 2015), (Ram, 2017)	Y
Structures	98	5		Combined Business/IT Strategy Committee at CxO level [98]	(MacDorman & Gulzar, 2017)	
Processes	99	5	Business integration practices to enable converging business and IT in structure and strategy (Horlach 2018)	Strategic planning of IT Strategy, together with Business (based on product-lines) [99]	(MacDorman & Gulzar, 2017)	Y
Structures	100	4,5	Specific Agile roles in job structures and formal documentation of corresponding responsibilities	Training in Agile, organized through normal (HR) channels [100] [104]	(Horlach et al., 2017a)	
Processes	101	1,2,3,4,5		customer needs to specify his IT service requirements	(Sprokholt, 2016)	
Relational Mechanism	102	1,2,3,4,5	Development of IT- and Business-Convergence in the organization (Horlach, 2018)	the influence of the location from where the services are delivered (off-/nearshore, onsite etc)	(Sprokholt, 2016)	
Processes	103	1,2,3,4,5	Agile practices used as replacement of traditional project management techniques and methods	use of agile development methods	(Sprokholt, 2016)	
Processes	104	3,4,5	Agile practices used as replacement of traditional project management techniques and methods	training in Agile development methods	(Sprokholt, 2016)	
Processes	105	1,2,3,4,5		Identification of culture types based on Cameron & Quinn (and mapping to business activity type)	(Sprokholt & Wijers, 2016)	
Structures	105	1,2,3,4,5		Classifying business activities (creation of structures)	(Sprokholt & Wijers, 2016)	
Processes	106	1,2,3,4,5		Mapping Service typology to business activity	(Sprokholt & Wijers, 2016)	

Bimodal IT Governance							36 governance practices used in this research
Item	ID	Archetype	Bimodal Governance Practice	SPRM description	Reference		
Relational Mechanism	107	1,2,3,4,5		IT Leadership Leadership and Steering layer to lead and govern IT. The main responsibility at this layer is: to set a digital vision and strategy, to define priorities and investment selection, to design an architecture driven by the key IT services needed to support the business activities, systems and data, to manage the key IT capabilities and sourcing, to manage the cohesion and consistency across the organization, and to set policies and requirements with regard to compliance, security and continuity	(Sprokolt & Wijers, 2016)	Y	
Relational Mechanism	108	4,5	Development of IT- and Business-Convergence in the organization (Horlach, 2018)	Manage and locate Business IT teams close to business units (co-location)	(Sprokolt & Wijers, 2016)		
Relational Mechanism	109	4,5	Development of IT- and Business-Convergence in the organization (Horlach, 2018)	short communication lines and to share knowledge easily	(Sprokolt & Wijers, 2016)		
Structures	110	1,2,3,4,5		CIO office and its capabilities will be organized under the CIO centrally and will give direction to the IT vision and strategy of the company by providing enterprise architecture and standards	(Sprokolt & Wijers, 2016)	Y	
Processes	111	1,2,3,4,5		IT service portfolio and the project portfolio are also centrally managed by the CIO Office	(Sprokolt & Wijers, 2016)		
Processes	112	1,2,3,4,5		budget allocation mechanism (capacity allocation) which directs resources to business IT services and to platform IT services	(Sprokolt & Wijers, 2016)		
Structures	113	4,5	Digital expertise and clear division of accountabilities at executive level between exploitation and exploration collaborating towards business and IT convergence	Competent Digital Leadership a.k.a. CDO	(Fenwick & Martin Gill, 2013)	Y	
Structures	114	4,5	Digital expertise and clear division of accountabilities at executive level between exploitation and exploration collaborating towards business and IT convergence	Competent / skilled board at CxO level	(Fenwick & Martin Gill, 2013)		
Structures	115	4,5		Use a (business) Program Management Office	(Fenwick & Martin Gill, 2013)	Y	
Processes	116	4,5		Use a coordinated business and IT change management function	(Fenwick & Martin Gill, 2013)		
Relational Mechanism	117	4,5	Development of IT- and Business-Convergence in the organization (Horlach, 2018)	Organize teams in customer-oriented product lines, not projects	(Fenwick & Martin Gill, 2013)		
Relational Mechanism	118	4,5	Development of IT- and Business-Convergence in the organization (Horlach, 2018)	Embed digital skills and competencies into the business	(Fenwick & Martin Gill, 2013)		
Structures	119	4,5	Specific Agile roles in job structures and formal documentation of corresponding responsibilities	Use Agile all the way (Marketing, IT, HR, ..., product design, eBusiness)	(Fenwick & Martin Gill, 2013)		
Structures	120	4,5	Specific Agile roles in job structures and formal documentation of corresponding responsibilities	Embed architects in business/technology teams with advisory skills over architecture skills	(Barnett, 2018)		
Processes	121	4,5	Business integration practices to enable converging business and IT in structure and strategy (Horlach 2018)	EA create a pragmatic roadmap and change portfolio	(Barnett, 2018)		
Processes	122	4,5	Agile practices used as replacement of traditional project management techniques and methods	Architecture products also customer-product oriented rather than domain or program/project oriented. (using agile techniques, vgl Lean, Kanban, Agile, SAFe etc.)	(Barnett, 2018)		
Structures	123	3,4,5	Specific Agile roles in job structures and formal documentation of corresponding responsibilities	Agile Architects	(Barnett, 2018)	Y	
Relational Mechanism	124	1,2,3,4,5		Leading by example	(Clarke, Morgan, Beeson, & Stern, 2018)	Y	
Structures	125	4,5	Digital expertise and clear division of accountabilities at executive level between exploitation and exploration collaborating towards business and IT convergence	Appoint a CDO to drive change	(Gill & Jessee, 2018)		
Relational Mechanism	126	4,5		Leading by example [124]	(Gill & Jessee, 2018)		
Structures	127	4,5		Competent / skilled board, CxO level	(Gill & Jessee, 2018)	Y	
Relational Mechanism	128	4,5	Development of IT- and Business-Convergence in the organization (Horlach, 2018)	Organize teams in customer-oriented product lines, not projects vgl	(Gill & Jessee, 2018)		
Structures	129	3,4		Competent / skilled board, CxO level	(Berdak & Giudice, 2016)		
Processes	130	3,4		Transitional Architecture incl. evolving Systems of Record	(Berdak & Giudice, 2016)		
Processes	131	3,4	Agile practices used as replacement of traditional project management techniques and methods	Extend Agile to your IT Operations (use DevOps)	(Berdak & Giudice, 2016)		
Relational Mechanism	132	3,4	Development of IT- and Business-Convergence in the organization (Horlach, 2018)	Real multi disciplinary teams incl. Test and Operations people	(Berdak & Giudice, 2016)	Y	
Relational Mechanism	133	3,4	IT originating body taking the lead in bidirectional collaboration between Business and IT to enable convergence (Horlach 2018)	Agile product owners from the business	(Berdak & Giudice, 2016)		
Processes	134	3,4		PMO	(Berdak & Giudice, 2016)		
Relational Mechanism	135	3,4	Development of IT- and Business-Convergence in the organization (Horlach, 2018)	Build cross-functional (multidisciplinary) teams.	(Berdak & Giudice, 2016)		
Processes	136	3,4		Release management	(Berdak & Giudice, 2016)		
Processes	137	3,4		Change management	(Berdak & Giudice, 2016)		
Processes	138	3,4		Deployment management	(Berdak & Giudice, 2016)		
Processes	139	3,4		Prototyping	(Berdak & Giudice, 2016)		
Processes	140	4,5		DevOps	(Giudice & Condo, 2017)		
Processes	141	3,4		Transformational Architecture Mgt	(Blumberg, Bossert, & Laartz, 2016), (Dias, Khanna, et al., 2017), (Swaminathan & Meffert, 2017)		
Processes	142	3,4	Business integration practices to enable converging business and IT in structure and strategy (Horlach 2018)	Business Strategy, prioritized to two-speeds	(Blumberg, Bossert, & Laartz, 2016), (Dias, Khanna, et al., 2017), (Swaminathan & Meffert, 2017)		
Relational Mechanism	143	3,4,5	Development of IT- and Business-Convergence in the organization (Horlach, 2018)	Multi disciplinary teams	(Dias, Hamilton, Paquette, & Sood, 2017), (Dias, Khanna, et al., 2017), (McKinsey & Company, 2018), (Swaminathan & Meffert, 2017)		
Processes	144	3,4,5		Modular and flexible architecture	(Dias, Hamilton, Paquette, & Sood, 2017), (Dias, Khanna, et al., 2017), (McKinsey & Company, 2018), (Swaminathan & Meffert, 2017)		
Processes	145	3,4,5		Modular and flexible software delivery process	(Dias, Hamilton, Paquette, & Sood, 2017), (Dias, Khanna, et al., 2017), (McKinsey & Company, 2018), (Swaminathan & Meffert, 2017)		
Processes	146	3,4,5	Nontraditional metrics focused on digital adoption and external value creation	Performance Management from top to bottom, with metrics and KPI's for employees at all levels	(Dias, Hamilton, Paquette, & Sood, 2017), (Dias, Khanna, et al., 2017), (McKinsey & Company, 2018), (Swaminathan & Meffert, 2017)	Y	
Processes	147	3,4,5	Agile practices used as replacement of traditional project management techniques and methods	Agile organization all the way	(Dias, Hamilton, Paquette, & Sood, 2017), (Dias, Khanna, et al., 2017), (McKinsey & Company, 2018), (Swaminathan & Meffert, 2017)		
Processes	148	4,5	Adapted funding principles tailored to rapid Agile delivery cycles	Venture Capital (funding) principle vgl [85]	(Bhappkar, Dias, Elzenman, Floretta, & Rohr, 2017), (Dias, Khanna, et al., 2017), (Swaminathan & Meffert, 2017)		
Processes	149	4,5		Sourcing mainly on technical expertise	(Bhappkar, Dias, Elzenman, Floretta, & Rohr, 2017), (Dias, Khanna, et al., 2017), (Swaminathan & Meffert, 2017)		

Bimodal IT Governance							36 governance practices used in this research
Item	ID	Archetype	Bimodal Governance Practice	SPRM description	Reference		
Relational Mechanism	150	4,5	Development of IT- and Business-Convergence in the organization (Horlach, 2018)	Rotating people across teams	(Bhappkar, Dias, Eizenman, Floretta, & Rohr, 2017), (Dias, Khanna, et al., 2017), (Swaminathan & Meffert, 2017)		
Relational Mechanism	151	4,5	Development of IT- and Business-Convergence in the organization (Horlach, 2018)	Multi disciplinary teams	(Bhappkar, Dias, Eizenman, Floretta, & Rohr, 2017), (Dias, Khanna, et al., 2017), (Swaminathan & Meffert, 2017)		
Processes	152	4,5	Business integration practices to enable converging business and IT in structure and strategy (Horlach 2018)	Business Strategy, prioritized to "things to do" for the digital transformation	(Bhappkar, Dias, Eizenman, Floretta, & Rohr, 2017), (Dias, Khanna, et al., 2017), (Swaminathan & Meffert, 2017)		
Structures	153	4,5		investment Committee [46]	(Bhappkar, Dias, Eizenman, Floretta, & Rohr, 2017), (Dias, Khanna, et al., 2017), (Swaminathan & Meffert, 2017)		
Processes	154	4,5	Agile practices used as replacement of traditional project management techniques and methods	Agile organization all the way	(Bhappkar, Dias, Eizenman, Floretta, & Rohr, 2017), (Dias, Khanna, et al., 2017), (Swaminathan & Meffert, 2017)		
Processes	155	4,5		Changemanagement (-Plan)	(Bhappkar, Dias, Eizenman, Floretta, & Rohr, 2017), (Dias, Khanna, et al., 2017), (Swaminathan & Meffert, 2017)		
Processes	156	4,5	Nontraditional metrics focused on digital adoption and external value creation	Performance Management	(Bhappkar, Dias, Eizenman, Floretta, & Rohr, 2017), (Dias, Khanna, et al., 2017), (Swaminathan & Meffert, 2017)		
Structures	157	4,5		skilled (Agile) Leaders on the Board / CxO level	(Bhappkar, Dias, Eizenman, Floretta, & Rohr, 2017), (Dias, Khanna, et al., 2017), (Swaminathan & Meffert, 2017)		
Structures	158	4,5	Digital expertise and clear division of accountabilities at executive level between exploitation and exploration collaborating towards business and IT convergence	Appoint a CDO to drive change	(Bhappkar, Dias, Eizenman, Floretta, & Rohr, 2017), (Dias, Khanna, et al., 2017), (Swaminathan & Meffert, 2017)		
Processes	159	4,5		Portfolio Mgt (Prioritized) with Business and IT	(Desmet, Markovitch, & Paquette, 2015), (Dias, Khanna, et al., 2017), (Swaminathan & Meffert, 2017)		
Processes	160	4,5		Release management, separate release moments for each speed	(Desmet, Markovitch, & Paquette, 2015), (Dias, Khanna, et al., 2017), (Swaminathan & Meffert, 2017)		
Processes	161	4,5		Sourcing mainly on technical expertise	(Desmet, Markovitch, & Paquette, 2015), (Dias, Khanna, et al., 2017), (Swaminathan & Meffert, 2017)		
Processes	162	4,5		budget allocation to increase organization flexibility	(Desmet, Markovitch, & Paquette, 2015), (Dias, Khanna, et al., 2017), (Swaminathan & Meffert, 2017)		
Processes	163	4,5	Agile practices used as replacement of traditional project management techniques and methods	Agile development	(Desmet, Markovitch, & Paquette, 2015), (Dias, Khanna, et al., 2017), (Swaminathan & Meffert, 2017)		
Structures	164	4,5		skilled (Agile) Leaders	(Desmet, Markovitch, & Paquette, 2015), (Dias, Khanna, et al., 2017), (Swaminathan & Meffert, 2017)		
Relational Mechanism	165	4,5	IT originating body taking the lead in bidirectional collaboration between Business and IT to enable convergence (Horlach 2018)	Demonstrations (demo's)	(Desmet, Markovitch, & Paquette, 2015), (Dias, Khanna, et al., 2017), (Swaminathan & Meffert, 2017)		
Processes	166	4,5		Roadmap (prioritized) - related to the portfolio of the organization	(Desmet, Markovitch, & Paquette, 2015), (Dias, Khanna, et al., 2017), (Swaminathan & Meffert, 2017)		
Processes	167	4,5		Sourcing mainly on technical expertise	(Desmet, Markovitch, & Paquette, 2015), (Dias, Khanna, et al., 2017), (Swaminathan & Meffert, 2017)		
Relational Mechanism	168	4,5	Development of IT- and Business-Convergence in the organization (Horlach, 2018)	Sourcing (done by Vendor) for building teams when scaling Agile	(Desmet, Markovitch, & Paquette, 2015), (Dias, Khanna, et al., 2017), (Swaminathan & Meffert, 2017)		
Processes	169	4,5	Nontraditional metrics focused on digital adoption and external value creation	Performance Management	(Desmet, Markovitch, & Paquette, 2015), (Dias, Khanna, et al., 2017), (Swaminathan & Meffert, 2017)		
Relational Mechanism	170	4,5	Development of IT- and Business-Convergence in the organization (Horlach, 2018)	Multi disciplinary teams	(Desmet, Markovitch, & Paquette, 2015), (Dias, Khanna, et al., 2017), (Swaminathan & Meffert, 2017)		
Structures	171	4,5	Digital expertise and clear division of accountabilities at executive level between exploitation and exploration collaborating towards business and IT convergence	Appoint a CDO to drive change	(Dahlström, Desmet, & Singer, 2017), (McKinsey & Company, 2018), (Swaminathan & Meffert, 2017)		
Structures	172	4,5		skilled (Agile) Leaders	(Dahlström, Desmet, & Singer, 2017), (McKinsey & Company, 2018), (Swaminathan & Meffert, 2017)		
Processes	173	4,5	Adapted funding principles tailored to rapid Agile delivery cycles	Venture Capital (funding) principle vgl [85]	(Dahlström, Desmet, & Singer, 2017), (McKinsey & Company, 2018), (Swaminathan & Meffert, 2017)		
Processes	174	4,5	Business integration practices to enable converging business and IT in structure and strategy (Horlach 2018)	Business Strategy, prioritized to "things to do" for the digital transformation	(Dahlström, Desmet, & Singer, 2017), (McKinsey & Company, 2018), (Swaminathan & Meffert, 2017)		

7.9 Appendix I – Bimodal IT governance practices including literature reference

Bimodal IT Governance							
Item	ID	Originating ID	Found in archetypes	Bimodal Governance Practice	Relate to traditional governance practice	SPRM description	Reference
Structures	BGS1	"21", "32", "113", "114", "125", "158", "171"	4,5	Digital expertise and clear division of accountabilities at executive level between exploitation and exploration collaborating towards business and IT convergence	S2,S4,S5	"Existence of a CDO function [21], CIO and CDO on CxO level and reporting to CEO/COO", "CIO on CxO level, responsible for Agile Delivery [32]", "Competent Digital Leadership a.k.a. CDO", "Competent / skilled board at CxO level"	"(Horlach et al., 2017a)", "(Fenwick & Martin Gill, 2013)", "(Gill & Jesse, 2018)", "(Bhaskar, Dias, Eizenman, Floretta, & Rohr, 2017)", "(Dias, Khanna, et al., 2017)", "(Swaminathan & Meffert, 2017)", "(Dahlström, Desmet, & Singer, 2017)", "(McKinsey & Company, 2018)"
Structures	BGS2	"64", "65", "92", "93", "94", "95", "100", "119", "120", "123"	3,4,5	Specific Agile roles in job structures and formal documentation of corresponding responsibilities	S11, S12	"Design Authority [64]", "Product Owner [65]", "Centralized Data & Analytics [92]", "Centralized Customer Interaction [93]", "Mobile Center of Excellence (App dev.) [94]", "Agile Staff (initiate/promote culture) [95]", "Training in Agile, organized through normal (HR) channels [100]", "Use Agile all the way (Marketing, IT, HR, ..., product design, eBusiness, operations)", "Embed architects in business/technology teams with advisory skills over architecture skills.", "Agile Architects"	"(MacDorman & Gulzar, 2017)", "(Bayley & Shacklady, 2015)", "(Behar, Weber, & Simone, 2015)", "(Ram, 2017)", "(Horlach et al., 2017a)", "(Fenwick & Martin Gill, 2013)", "(Barnett, 2018)"
Processes	BGP1	"18", "24", "26", "34", "54", "57", "58", "59", "62", "63", "66", "67", "68", "69", "70", "71", "72", "73", "74", "80", "81", "87", "88", "103", "104", "122", "131", "147", "154", "163"	1,2,3,4,5	Agile practices used as replacement of traditional project management techniques and methods	P8	"Traditional (IT) program- and Project Management methodology, mixed with Agile project management (dual PM's) [18]", "Agile (IT) program- and Project Management methodology [24]", "Framework SAFe [26]", "Project Management methodology [34]", "User Group [54] Steering committee. In existence a structure, logged as process due to the function in replacing/supporting traditional Project Steering in Agile environments", "Backlog [57]", "Sprint [58]", "User Stories [59]", "Agile (IT) Program Management methodology- [62]", "Product Prototyping [63]", "Iterative / Incremental Development & SAFe [66]", "Extreme Programming XP [67]", "Scrum [68]", "DAD [69]", "Kanban [70]", "Scrumban [71]", "Lean Startup [72]", "LeSS [73]", "Nexus [74]", "Framework SAFe [80]", "Focus on products, not projects [81]", "Focus on organizational transition from project (short term, myopic, limited scope), to product (long term, resource efficiency)", "Agile development [87]", "DevOps [88]", "training in Agile development methods", "Architecture products also customer - product oriented rather than domain or program/project oriented. (using agile techniques, vgl Lean, Kanban, Agile, SAFe etc etc)", "Extend Agile to your IT Operations (use DevOps)", "Agile organization all the way", "Agile development"	"(Mingay, Mesaglio, & Scott, 2016)", "(Bayley & Shacklady, 2015)", "(Behar, Weber, & Simone, 2015)", "(Ram, 2017)", "(Bhaskar, Dias, Eizenman, Floretta, & Rohr, 2017)", "(Dias, Khanna, et al., 2017)", "(Swaminathan & Meffert, 2017)", "(Dahlström, Desmet, & Singer, 2017)", "(McKinsey & Company, 2018)", "(Swaminathan & Meffert, 2017)"
Processes	BGP2	"33", "75", "76", "99", "121", "142", "152", "174"	3,4,5	Business integration practices to enable converging business and IT in structure and strategy (Horlach 2018)	P1,P3	"Portfolio Mgt with Business (BC, ROI, Information Economics, Value creation [33]", "Bimodal Program- and Portfolio Mgt [75]", "PPM building a Roadmap [76]", "Strategic planning of IT Strategy, together with Business (based on product-lines) [99]", "EA create a pragmatic roadmap and change portfolio", "Business strategy, prioritized to two-speeds", "Business Strategy, prioritized to 'things to do' for the digital transformation", "Business Strategy, prioritized to 'things to do' for the digital transformation"	"(Horlach et al., 2017a)", "(Leffingwell, 2017)", "(MacDorman & Gulzar, 2017)", "(Holz, 2017)", "(Mingay, Mesaglio, & Scott, 2016)", "(Mingay, Mesaglio, & Scott, 2016)", "(Bayley & Shacklady, 2015)", "(Behar, Weber, & Simone, 2015)", "(Ram, 2017)", "(Sprokholz, 2016)", "(Barnett, 2018)", "(Berdak & Giudice, 2016)", "(Dias, Hamilton, Paquette, & Sood, 2017)", "(Dias, Khanna, et al., 2017)", "(McKinsey & Company, 2018)", "(Swaminathan & Meffert, 2017)", "(Bhaskar, Dias, Eizenman, Floretta, & Rohr, 2017)", "(Desmet, Markovitch, & Paquette, 2015)"
Processes	BGP3	"82", "85", "86", "148", "173"	4,5	Adapted funding principles tailored to rapid Agile delivery cycles	P9	"Separate IT Budget Control and Reporting for mode 1 and mode 2", "funding per product/team [82]", "funding per product/team [82]", "Venture Capital (funding) principle [85]", "Flexible/dynamic decision and budget cycles [86]", "Venture Capital (funding) principle/Venture Capital (funding) principle"	"(Horlach et al., 2017a)", "(Hanford, 2016)", "(MacDorman & Gulzar, 2017)", "(Barnett, 2018)", "(Blumberg, Bossert, & Laartz, 2016)", "(Dias, Khanna, et al., 2017)", "(Swaminathan & Meffert, 2017)", "(Bhaskar, Dias, Eizenman, Floretta, & Rohr, 2017)", "(Dahlström, Desmet, & Singer, 2017)", "(McKinsey & Company, 2018)"
Processes	BGP4	"146", "156", "169"	3,4,5	Nontraditional metrics focused on digital adoption and external value creation	P2	"Performance Management from top to bottom, with metrics and KPI's for employees at all levels", "Performance Management", "Performance Management"	"(Dias, Hamilton, Paquette, & Sood, 2017)", "(Dias, Khanna, et al., 2017)", "(McKinsey & Company, 2018)", "(Swaminathan & Meffert, 2017)", "(Bhaskar, Dias, Eizenman, Floretta, & Rohr, 2017)", "(Desmet, Markovitch, & Paquette, 2015)"
Relational Mechanism	BGR1	"1", "9", "13", "16", "37", "40", "78", "79", "102", "108", "109", "117", "118", "128", "132", "135", "143", "150", "151", "168", "170"	1,2,3,4,5	Development of IT- and Business-Convergence in the organization (Horlach, 2018)	R1,R2,R3,R5	"Knowledge Sharing by developers during handover [01]", "Co-location of project team within company [09]", "Direct interaction among project managers is ensured by locally centralizing all people in a department with fixed workplaces. [13]", "Outsourcing (adaptive) project teams [16], Outsourcing partners deliver solely the skilled teams", "Knowledge Sharing is common, due to use frameworks like Spotify (Guilds) [37]", "Dedicated Supervisor for personnel development [40]", "Workshops, Proof of Concepts and Demo's [78]", "Job Rotation between Mode 1 and Mode 2 [79]", "the influence of the location from where the services are delivered (off / nearshore, onsite etc)", "Manage and locate Business IT teams close to business units (co-location)", "short communication lines and to share knowledge easily", "Organize teams in customer-oriented product lines, not projects", "Embed digital skills and competencies into the business", "Organize teams in customer-oriented product lines, not projects vgl [117]", "Real multi disciplinary teams incl. Test and Operations people", "Build cross-functional (multidisciplinary) teams", "Multi disciplinary teams", "Rotating people across teams", "Multi disciplinary teams", "Sourcing (done by Vendor) for building teams when scaling Agile", "Multi disciplinary teams"	"(Horlach et al., 2017a)", "(Kniberg Henrik; Ivarsson Anders, 2012)", "(Mingay, Mesaglio, & Scott, 2016)", "(Sprokholz, 2016)", "(Sprokholz & Wijers, 2016)", "(Fenwick & Martin Gill, 2013)", "(Gill & Jesse, 2018)", "(Berdak & Giudice, 2016)", "(Dias, Hamilton, Paquette, & Sood, 2017)", "(Dias, Khanna, et al., 2017)", "(McKinsey & Company, 2018)", "(Swaminathan & Meffert, 2017)", "(Bhaskar, Dias, Eizenman, Floretta, & Rohr, 2017)", "(Desmet, Markovitch, & Paquette, 2015)", "(Dias, Khanna, et al., 2017)", "(Swaminathan & Meffert, 2017)"
Relational Mechanism	BGR2	"2", "12", "14", "17", "28", "55", "56", "83", "133", "165"	1,3,4,5	IT originating body taking the lead in bidirectional collaboration between Business and IT to enable convergence (Horlach 2018)	R3,R5	"Business-IT alignment, Project Mgt for Agile B-IT alignment [02]", "Business/IT alignment, through requirements engineering [12]", "Business/IT alignment, through individual project managers [14]", "Business/IT alignment, through project management office. Can be enhanced with Business role (program manager) [17]", "Business/IT alignment due to widely adapted Agile and thus corporation between IT and Business [28]", "Business-IT Relation manager [53]", "(Business) Sponsor [56] (aka Product Owner) [65]", "Product Mgt [83] referring to role of (senior / chief) Product Owner [65]", "Agile product owners from the business", "Demonstrations (demo's)"	"(Horlach et al., 2017a)", "(MacDorman & Gulzar, 2017)", "(Mingay, Mesaglio, & Scott, 2016)", "(Berdak & Giudice, 2016)", "(Desmet, Markovitch, & Paquette, 2015)", "(Dias, Khanna, et al., 2017)", "(Swaminathan & Meffert, 2017)"

7.10 Appendix J – List of obtained organizational documentation

Obtained documentation	
Organization 1	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. IT Strategy document 2. IT-standards document
Organization 2	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Organization blueprint 2018 2. IT-vision document for reorganization of IT 2012 3. IT-vision document for mode 2 part of the organization 2014 4. IT-vision document for department of infrastructure services 2017-2020 5. Management presentation - New IT organization planning 2014-2018
Organization 3	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. @@ 2. @@
Organization 4	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Email with general company info 2. Organization blueprint 2018 3. Strategic Roadmap 2018 4. Tactical Roadmap 2018 5. Infrastructure Architecture Framework (Appendix Roadmap 2018)
Organization 5	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Organization blueprint 2018 2. Strategic Portfolio 2018; 3. Strategic Architecture 2018 4. Strategic / Tactical Roadmap 2018
Organization 6	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Organization blueprint 2018 2. Organization strategy plan 3. Description of work processes 4. Report investigation 'Algemene Rekenkamer' on ICT-Governance 5. Factsheet IT Department
Organization 7	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Email with general company info 2. Organization blueprint 2018 3. Digital Strategy 2018 (Strategy and Portfolio) 4. Enterprise Architecture 2018
Organization 8	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Email with general company info 2. Organization blueprint 2018 3. Strategic vision document, incl. Portfolio 4. Enterprise Architecture 2018

7.11 Appendix K – SPRM distribution across Bimodal governance practices

All governance practices per organization	Org. A Arch. 1	Org. B Arch. 3	Org. C Arch. 4	Org. D Arch. 4	Org. E Arch. 4	Org. F Arch. 5	Org. G Arch. 5	Org. H Arch. 4
Knowledge Sharing by developers during handover [01]	Y,M,D	Y,M,D,O,B	Y,M,D,O,B	Y,M,D,O	Y,M,D,O,B	Y,M,D,O	Y,M,D,O,B	Y,M,D,O,B
Business-IT alignment, Project Mgt for Agile B-IT alignment [02]	Y,M,D	N,,	Y,M,D,O,B	Y,M,D,B	Y,M,D,B	Y,M,D,O	Y,M,D,O,B	Y,M,D,B
IT Steering Committee (traditional) for Mode 1 and Mode 2 [03]; [10]; [22]	Y,G,D,B	Y,G,D,B	Y,G,D,B	Y,G,D,B	Y,G,D,B	Y,G,D	Y,G,D,B	Y,G,D,B
IT Steering Committee (traditional) for Outsourced projects by contracts & agreements [04]; [11]	Y,M,D,B	Y,G,D,O,B	Y,M,D,B	Y,M,D	Y,M,D,B	Y,M,D	Y,M,B	Y,M,D,B
IT Budget Control and Reporting, per Business project [05], [43]; [19]	Y,M,D,B	Y,M,D,B	Y,G,D,B	Y,M,D,B	Y,M,D,B	Y,M,D	Y,G,D,B	Y,G,D,B
Portfolio Management (BC, ROI, Information Economics, Value creation). Complex Portfolio management. IT is responsible for condensing the separate portfolio's into one overall portfolio [06]	Y,M,D	Y,G,D,B	Y,G,D,B	Y,G,D,B	Y,G,D,B	Y,M,D,B	Y,G,D,B	Y,G,D,B
Outsourcing to reduce time to market (adaptive) [08];	Y,M,D	Y,M,D,B	Y,M,D,B	Y,M,D,B	Y,M,D,O,B	Y,M,D,O	Y,M,D,O,B	Y,M,D,O,B
Co-location of project team within company [09]	N,,	Y,M,D,B	Y,M,D,B	Y,M,D,O	Y,M,D,O,B	N,,	Y,M,D,O,B	Y,M,D,B
Traditional (IT) program- and Project Management methodology, mixed with Agile project management (dual PM's) [18]; [34]	N,,	Y,M,D,B	Y,M,D,B	Y,M,D,B	Y,M,D,B	Y,M,D	Y,M,D,B	Y,M,D,B
Existence of a CDO function [21], CIO and CDO [21] on CxO level and reporting to CEO/COO	N,,	N,,	Y,G,D,B	Y,G,D,B	Y,G,D,B	Y,G,D	Y,G,D,B	Y,G,D,B
Product Owner, Scrum Master [25]	N,,	Y,M,D,B	Y,M,D,B	Y,M,D,B	Y,M,D,B	Y,M,D	Y,M,D,B	Y,M,D,B
Business/IT alignment due to corporation between CIO and CDO [29]	N,,	N,,	Y,G,D,O,B	N,,	N,,	N,,	N,,	N,,
Portfolio Mgt with Business (BC, ROI, Information Economics, Value creation [60]) [33], [61]	Y,M,B	Y,M,D,B	Y,M,D,B	Y,M,D,B	Y,M,D,B	Y,M,D,B	Y,G,D,B	Y,G,D,B
Managers for coaching teams [38]	N,,							
Architecture Review Board [41]	N,,	N,,	Y,,	Y,M,D	Y,G,D	Y,M,D	Y,G,D,B	Y,G,D
Chargeback arrangements [45]	N,,	N,,	N,,	N,,	N,,	Y,M,D,O	Y,M,D,O,B	N,,
IT Business / Executive council [47]	N,,	N,,	N,,	N,,	N,,	N,,	Y,G,B	N,,
Program Management Office [49]	N,,	N,,	Y,M,D	Y,M,D	Y,M,D,B	N,,	Y,M,D,B	Y,M,D
Risk Advisory Board [51]	N,,	N,,	N,,	Y,M,D,B	Y,M,D,B	N,,	N,,	Y,M,B
Design Authority [64]	N,,	N,,	Y,M,D	Y,M,D	Y,M,D,B	Y,M,D	Y,M,D,O,B	Y,M,D,B
Workshops, Proof of Concepts and Demo's [78]	Y,M,D	N,,	Y,M,D,B	Y,M,D,O	Y,M,D,O,B	Y,M,D,O	Y,M,D,O,B	Y,M,D,O,B
Job Rotation between Mode 1 and Mode 2 [79]	N,,	N,,	Y,M,D,B	N,,	Y,M,D	N,,	Y,M,D	N,,
Separate IT Budget Control and Reporting for mode 1 and mode 2 [27], or funding per product/team [82]; Funding per product/team [82]	N,,	Y,G,B	Y,G,D,B	N,,	N,,	N,,	Y,G,B	N,,
Technology driven Product Mgt and Innovation Mgt [84]; (context of product mgt: long term, resource efficiency)	N,,	Y,G,D,B						
Security Strategy [96]	Y,M,B							
Security Governance [97]	N,,	Y,G,D,O,B	Y,G,D,O,B	Y,G,D,O,B	Y,G,D,O,B	Y,G,D,O	Y,G,D,O,B	Y,G,D,O,B
Strategic planning of IT Strategy, together with Business (based on product-lines) [99]	N,,	Y,G,D,B	Y,G,D,B	Y,G,D,B	Y,G,D,B	Y,G,B	Y,G,D,B	Y,G,B
IT Leadership Leadership and Steering layer to lead and govern IT. The main responsibility at this layer is: to set a digital vision and strategy, to define priorities and investment selection, to design an architecture driven by the key IT services needed to support the business activities, systems and data, to manage the key IT capabilities and sourcing, to manage the cohesion and consistency across the organization, and to set policies and requirements with regard to compliance, security and continuity	Y,G,D,O,B	Y,G,D,O,B	Y,G,D,O,B	Y,G,D,O,B	Y,G,D,O,B	Y,G,D,O	Y,G,D,O,B	Y,G,D,O,B
CIO office and its capabilities will be organized under the CIO centrally and will give direction to the IT vision and strategy of the company by providing enterprise architecture and standards	N,,	N,,	Y,G,D,B	Y,G,D,B	Y,G,D,O,B	N,,	Y,G,D,O,B	Y,G,D,B
Competent Digital Leadership a.k.a. CDO	N,,	N,,	Y,G,D,O,B	N,,	Y,G,D,B	Y,G,D,O,B	Y,G,D,O,B	Y,G,D,B
Use a (business) Program Management Office	N,,							
Agile Architects	N,,	N,,	Y,G,D,B	N,,	Y,M,D,B	N,,	Y,M,D,B	N,,
Leading by example	Y,M,B	Y,M,D,B	Y,M,D,O,B	Y,M,D,B	Y,M,D,O,B	Y,M,D,O	Y,M,D,O,B	Y,M,D,O,B
Competent / skilled board, CxO level	N,,	N,,	Y,G,D,B	N,,	N,,	Y,G,D,O	Y,G,D,O,B	Y,G,B
Real multi disciplinary teams incl. Test and Operation	N,,	Y,M,D	Y,M,D	Y,M,D,O	Y,M,D,O,B	Y,M,D,O	Y,M,D,O,B	Y,M,D,O,B
Performance Management from top to bottom, with metrics and KPI's for employees at all levels	N,,	N,,	N,,	N,,	Y,G,D,O,B	N,,	Y,G,D,O,B	Y,G,D,B

7.12 Appendix L – SPRM mapping

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